

D2.3 - Implementation of the Back-End for R1, R2 and R3

WP2 Development of Computed Assisted Integral
Waste Management Systems

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the implementation of the Waste4Think Back-End platform as the middleware layer of the waste operation and management system architecture defined in the deliverable D2.1 [3]. The Back-End platform implemented is mainly based on the FIWARE [1] Generic Enablers components and it is responsible for handling context information coming from the sensors deployed in the Waste4Think Pilots, as well as control instrumentation of the treatment plants, apps, learning material, serious game, and dispatching it to components that are in the Business / Service layer in order to support the results R1 “Operation and Management Module”, R2 “Collection Module”, R3 “Planning Module”.

The conceptual architecture of the Back-End Platform, instantiated in the FIWARE Lab Cloud Infrastructure, has been presented in this deliverable providing an overview of the features, that are briefly summarized as:

- management of context information;
- processing and analysis of real-time events and triggering of instantaneous predefined actions;
- storage of context information as historical data;
- publication of context information as open data;
- availability of a set of public and/or private APIs to retrieve both context information and historical data;
- authentication and authorization systems both for the pilots and front-end applications.

The work in this deliverable presents also all the activities needed to deploy and configure the Back-End Platform on the Spain 2 node of FIWARE Lab Cloud, through the defined Waste4Think Organization by providing a single entry point for the management of the Back-End platform, the creation and management of dedicated Security Group defining access rules to the virtual machines, the creation and management of Volumes that provide additional data storage attached to the virtual machines, the creation and management of Virtual Machines Images for the Waste4Think components.

Each of the Back-End services, as well as Security components, are also presented from the implementation point of view, including specific configuration and the deployment mechanisms put in place.

Finally, a description of the Back-End interfaces to others Waste4Think modules as sensors deployed to the pilots, treatment plants, apps, learning material, and serious game, has been included in this document.

Abbreviations

W4T	Waste4think
IDM	Identity Management System
GE	Generic Enabler
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
SSO	Single Sign On
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
XACML	eXtensible Access Control Markup Language
PDP	Policy Decision Point
VM	Virtual Machine
CEP	Complex Event Processing
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol

1. Introduction

This deliverable is focused on the implementation of the Waste4Think Back-End platform (see Figure 1) for the results R1 “Operation and Management Module, R2 “Collection Module”, R3 “Planning Module” and R4 “Circular Economy Model. The Back-End platform implemented is mainly based on FIWARE technologies [1].

Figure 1 - Back-End conceptual architecture

The four main subjects of the deliverable are:

- implementation of the Cloud infrastructure underlying the Back-End Platform;
- implementation of the Back-End services;
- implementation of the components to secure the Back-End platform;
- back-end interfaces to other Waste4Think Module.

Section 2 describes the conceptual architecture of the Back-End Platform.

Section 3 covers the activities carried out in the Cloud Infrastructure FIWARE Lab, to set-up the virtualised infrastructure underlying the Back-End Platform.

Section 4 describes the implementation of the Back-End components (FIWARE Generic Enablers and others) and in particular how each component has been installed, configured and managed.

Section 5 contains the installation and set-up of the FIWARE Generic Enablers to secure the Back-End Platform.

Finally, Section 6 covers the Back-End interfaces to sensors deployed to the pilots, treatment plants, serious game & apps, and learning material.

At the end of this deliverable, a series of Annexes about technical configurations and development activities carried out are included.

2. Waste4Think Back-End architecture

The objective of the WP2 “Development of computer assisted integral waste management system” is the definition and development of the ICT tools for improving the short and long-term waste management at local and territorial level as well as the planning and monitoring solutions of the different Zero Waste Environments of the Waste4Think project.

To achieve this objective and to support the results R1 “Operation and Management Module”, R2 “Collection Module”, R3 “Planning Module”, a Waste Management Back-End system has been deployed.

Figure 2. Back-End implementation

Figure 2 represents the implementation of the Waste Management Back-End system, instantiated in the FIWARE Lab Cloud Infrastructure (see section 3), which is able:

- to manage context information, through the FIWARE Orion Context Broker Generic Enabler (see section 4.3), coming from:
 - the sensors deployed in each of the Waste4Think pilots;
 - the control instrumentation of the Halandri treatment plants;
 - the serious game and other apps developed in the Waste4Think project;
 - learning materials.
- to process and analyse real-time events and triggering of instantaneous predefined actions (such as alerts and/or anomalies) through the CEP-Sandwich module (see section 4.5);

- to store context information as historical data on the time series DB InfluxDB (see section 4.6);
- to publish context information as open data, through the FIWARE Cygnus (see section 4.4) and CKAN Generic Enabler (see section 4.7);
- to provide a set of public and/or private APIs to retrieve both context information and historical data;
- to provide a web interface to operate over the data available both in the ORION Context broker and Historical module, through the CRUD module (see section 4.9).
- to provide authentication and authorization systems through a set of FIWARE security components (see section 5), specifically Identity Management KeyRock, PEP Proxy WILMA, and Authorization PDP AuthZForce;
- to provide a unique user entry point to the different applications in Waste4Think (Social Actions, Zero Waste Ecosystems, Planning Tool, Green Procurement, etc.), through the Admin back-end module (see section 4.8).

3. Cloud infrastructure implementation

3.1. FIWARE Lab

The Waste4Think Back-End has been deployed on FIWARE Lab infrastructure. FIWARE Lab is an open working instance of FIWARE available for experimentation based on OpenStack [2]. More details about FIWARE Lab can be found in Section 3 of the D2.1 [3].

All Waste4Think Back-End components have been provisioned and managed using the FIWARE Cloud capabilities of the FIWARE LAB node “Spain2”.

A Waste4Think Organization (see Figure 3) has been created to let more than one user access the shared cloud resources.

The screenshot displays the FIWARE Lab Identity Manager interface. The top navigation bar includes 'FIWARE Lab', 'Cloud', 'Store', 'Mashup', 'Data', 'Account', and 'Help/Info'. The user 'dario.pellegrino' is logged in. The main content area shows the 'Waste4Think' organization details, including a description, a list of members (dario.pellegrino, Pasquale Andriani, W4T Deusto), and a list of authorizing applications (Cloud and Store - OLD).

Members	
dario.pellegrino	
Pasquale Andriani	
W4T Deusto	

Authorizing Applications	
Cloud	http://cloud.lab.fiware.org/
Store - OLD	https://130.206.84.12/

Figure 3. FIWARE Lab Waste4Think Organization.

3.2. Access to FIWARE Lab

Two kinds of actors have access to the FIWARE LAB resources, as shown in Figure 4:

- the Admin that manage the whole FIWARE Cloud resources;
- the Service Consumer actor who is going to access and manage the deployed Back-End services.

Figure 4 - Access to the FIWARE Lab resources

3.2.1. Admin

The Admin actor is able to manage VMs, Security groups, Floating IPs and Keypairs. It accesses to the FIWARE Cloud resources through the global instance of FIWARE Identity Management GE [4] by using an authorized FIWARE account and then, through the Cloud Portal GE [5] (see Figure 5 and Figure 6).

The screenshot shows the FIWARE Lab Cloud Portal authentication interface. At the top is the FIWARE Lab logo and the text 'CLOUD PORTAL'. Below this is a 'Log In' section with a 'User Name' field containing 'dario.pellegrino@eng.it' and a 'Password' field with masked characters. At the bottom, there are three buttons: 'Request Community Account', 'Create Account', and 'Connect'.

Figure 5 – FIWARE Lab Cloud Portal authentication

Figure 6 – FIWARE Lab Cloud Portal

3.2.2. Service Consumer

The Service Consumer actor can access the Back-End services through an NGINX Reverse proxy [8]. All details about the NGINX service implementation and related configuration are defined in section 3.7 “*NGINX Reverse Proxy*” of this deliverable.

Access to both the Back-End services and Development Environment ports is granted with security rules defined by the Admin actor on Cloud Portal GE. More details about Waste4Think Security Group and rules can be found at section 3.4 “*Security groups*” of this deliverable.

3.3. Virtual Machines

The Waste4Think project on the FIWARE Lab (Spain2 Node) includes the following instances, also shown in Figure 7:

- **w4t backend prod:** the VM contains the mainly Back-End components as the Context Broker Orion [section 4.3], the connector Cygnus [section 4.4], the security components (IDM [section 5.3], AuthZForce [section 5.4] and PEP Proxy [section 5.2]) and NGINX Reverse proxy [section 3.7];
- **w4t suite:** the VM contains other Back-End components as the Historical DB InfluxDB, CEP-Sandwich module, CRUD, and those needed to support the operations of the different front-end modules in the Waste4Think ecosystem (Planning module, Invoice module, Green Procurement module, etc.)
- **w4t-opendata:** the VM contains the CKAN Instance [section 4.7];
- **w4t-dev:** the VM contains the development environment through a GitLab instance (see section 3.3 of the D2.1[3]).

Instances

Instance Name	Image Name	IP Address	Size	Key Pair	Status	Availability Zone	Task	Power State	Time since created	Actions
w4t-suite	base_ubuntu_16.04	192.168.235.170	m1.medium	w4t-keypair	Active	nova	None	Running	2 days, 22 hours	Create Snapshot
w4t_backend_prod	base_centos_7	192.168.229.62 Floating IPs: 130.206.117.164	m1.medium	w4t-keypair	Active	nova	None	Running	4 months	Create Snapshot
w4t-opendata	-	192.168.216.171	m1.medium	w4t-keypair	Active	nova	None	Running	7 months	Create Snapshot
w4t-dev	base_centos_7	192.168.240.164 Floating IPs: 130.206.120.215	m1.small	w4t-keypair	Active	nova	None	Running	1 year, 7 months	Create Snapshot

Displaying 4 items of False

Figure 7 – W4T VM instances

The two public IPs provided have been assigned to the Development Environment VM “w4t-dev” with IP 130.206.120.215 and to the VM “w4t-backend-prod” with IP 130.206.117.164.

Two third-level domains have been created to register both public IPs:

- backend.waste4think.eu → VM “w4t-backend-prod” (130.206.117.164);
- dev.waste4think.eu → VM “w4t-dev” with (130.206.120.215).

Figure 8 shows the physical network of the VMs deployed.

Figure 8 - VMs physical network

3.4. Security groups

A specific security group named “w4t-security-group” has been created to manage TCP traffic towards the VMs through specific ports.

Figure 9 - W4T Security Groups

Figure 10 shows the rules created in the Waste4Think context.

Manage Security Group Rules: w4t-security-group (78642238-87b5-4325-aa08-e19e6d3c14b2)

The screenshot shows the 'Manage Security Group Rules' page for the 'w4t-security-group'. It features a table with columns: Direction, Ether Type, IP Protocol, Port Range, Remote IP Prefix, Remote Security Group, and Actions. Each row has a 'Delete Rule' button. A tooltip 'Capture a Rectangular Region' is visible over the bottom right of the table.

Direction	Ether Type	IP Protocol	Port Range	Remote IP Prefix	Remote Security Group	Actions
Egress	IPv4	Any	Any	0.0.0.0/0	-	Delete Rule
Egress	IPv6	Any	Any	:::0	-	Delete Rule
Ingress	IPv4	TCP	22 (SSH)	0.0.0.0/0	-	Delete Rule
Ingress	IPv4	TCP	80 (HTTP)	0.0.0.0/0	-	Delete Rule
Ingress	IPv4	TCP	81	0.0.0.0/0	-	Delete Rule
Ingress	IPv4	TCP	82	0.0.0.0/0	-	Delete Rule
Ingress	IPv4	TCP	83	0.0.0.0/0	-	Delete Rule
Ingress	IPv4	TCP	3001	0.0.0.0/0	-	Delete Rule
Ingress	IPv4	TCP	5000	0.0.0.0/0	-	Delete Rule
Ingress	IPv4	TCP	8000	0.0.0.0/0	-	Delete Rule
Ingress	IPv4	TCP	8080	0.0.0.0/0	-	Delete Rule

Figure 10 - W4T Security Group rules

3.5. Volumes

As shown in Figure 11, three Volumes have been created to provide Waste4Think VMs an additional data storage space and in particular:

- w4t_volume_backend is a volume of 100GB attached to *w4t_backend_prod* VM and mounted on *./data* folder which is used to store data, logs and configuration files of the dockerized back-end services deployed on this VM;
- w4t-suite-volume is a volume of 50GB attached to *w4t-suite* VM and mounted on *./data* folder which is used to store data, logs and configuration files of the dockerized back-end services deployed on this VM;
- git-data-repo is a volume of 50GB attached to *w4t-dev* which is used to store the GITLab data.

Volumes

Name	Description	Size	Status	Type	Attached To	Availability Zone	Bootable	Encrypted	Actions
w4t-suite-volume	-	50GB	In-use	-	Attached to w4t-suite on /dev/vdb	nova	No	No	Edit Volume
w4t_volume_backend	-	100GB	In-use	-	Attached to w4t_backend_prod on /dev/vdb	nova	No	No	Edit Volume
git-data-repo	gitlab data repository	50GB	In-use	-	Attached to w4t-dev on /dev/vdc	nova	No	No	Edit Volume

Figure 11 - W4T Volumes

3.6. VMs images

Private VM images have been created in the Waste4Think organization for all the VMs used in the project (see Figure 12). These images can be re-used to deploy the Waste4Think Back-End platform in a fast and easy manner.

Images

Image Name	Type	Status	Public	Protected	Format	Size	Actions
w4t-suite-20180910	Snapshot	Active	No	No	QCOW2	1.8 GB	Launch Instance
w4t_orion_ald	Snapshot	Active	No	No	QCOW2	3.5 GB	Launch Instance
w4t_orion_prod_ald	Snapshot	Active	No	No	QCOW2	3.6 GB	Launch Instance
w4t_backend_prod_20180807	Snapshot	Active	No	No	QCOW2	17.6 GB	Launch Instance
w4t_dev_20180806	Snapshot	Active	No	No	QCOW2	20.0 GB	Launch Instance

Figure 12 – W4T VM images

3.7. NGINX Reverse Proxy

In the context of the Waste4Think project, NGINX [8] component has been used specifically as a Reverse Proxy [7] in order to retrieve resources on behalf of a Waste4Think Back-End user, from one or more servers within the internal network of the Waste4Think organization of FIWARE Lab.

3.7.1. Service overall description

NGINX [8] is an open source reverse proxy server for HTTP, HTTPS, SMTP, POP3, and IMAP protocols, as well as a load balancer, HTTP cache, and a web server (origin server).

3.7.2. Source code repository

The official NGINX source code repository is being hosted on GITHUB <https://github.com/nginx/nginx>.

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is hosted on DOCKER Hub at the following link https://hub.docker.com/r/_/nginx/.

3.7.3. Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think project, NGINX Reverse Proxy has been deployed by using Docker technologies.

Two different ways can be used to deploy the NGINX Reverse Proxy by using Docker.

- Installation by using docker cli command;
- Installation by using docker-compose.

In the context of the Waste4Think project, the docker-compose method has been used to deploy the NGINX Reverse Proxy.

Docker-compose method

In Table 1, the *docker-compose.yml* file used to deploy the NGINX Reverse Proxy in the Waste4Think Back-End environment. It creates a docker container NGINX and maps to an external volume the configuration file and log files.

```

version: "3"

services:
  nginx:
    image: nginx:latest

volumes:
  - data/docker_nginx/log/access.log:/var/log/nginx/access.log
  - /data/docker_nginx/log/error.log:/var/log/nginx/error.log
  - /data/docker_nginx/conf/w4t.conf:/etc/nginx/conf.d/default.conf

  ports:
    - "80:80"
    - "8080:8080"

networks:
  default:
    driver: bridge
    driver_opts:
      com.docker.network.driver.mtu: 1400

```

Table 1 – NGINX docker compose file

The installation is configured through the following parameters:

Image: The last version of the official NGINX service on Docker hub.

Volumes: Docker volumes has been created to map the following files to an external folder:

- NGINX log files;
- NGINX configuration file.

Ports: The NGINX service has been configured to run on port 80 and port 8080.

NGINX Configuration file

In Table 2, the NGINX configuration file is presented.

```
server {  
  
    listen      80;  
  
    server_name localhost;  
  
    client_max_body_size 100M;  
  
    location / {  
  
        proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;  
  
        proxy_set_header X-Forwarded-For $proxy_add_x_forwarded_for;  
  
        proxy_set_header Host $http_host;  
  
        proxy_set_header X-NginX-Proxy true;  
  
        proxy_pass http://192.168.229.62:82/;  
  
        proxy_redirect off;  
  
    }  
  
    location /connector {  
  
        proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;  
  
        proxy_set_header X-Forwarded-For $proxy_add_x_forwarded_for;  
  
        proxy_set_header Host $http_host;  
  
        proxy_set_header X-NginX-Proxy true;  
  
        proxy_pass https://192.168.229.62:3001/v1;  
  
        proxy_redirect off;  
  
    }  
  
}  
  
upstream ckan-webui {  
  
    server 192.168.216.171:8080;  
  
}  
  
server {  
  
    client_max_body_size 40M;  
  
    listen 8080;  
  
    server_name localhost;  
  
  
    location / {  
  
        proxy_pass http://ckan-webui;
```

```
proxy_redirect off;

proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;
proxy_set_header X-Forwarded-For $proxy_add_x_forwarded_for;
proxy_set_header Host $http_host;
proxy_set_header X-Nginx-Proxy true;

client_max_body_size 10m;
client_body_buffer_size 128k;
proxy_connect_timeout 90;
proxy_send_timeout 90;
proxy_read_timeout 90;
proxy_buffer_size 4k;
proxy_buffers 4 32k;
proxy_busy_buffers_size 64k;
proxy_temp_file_write_size 64k;

}
}
```

Table 2 - NGINX Configuration file

4. Back-End Services

4.1. Implementation of the Back-End services

Figure 13 - Back-End Services

The following FIWARE Generic Enablers and other third-party and custom components (see Figure 13) have been used and combined to implement the main services of the Back-end system as Context Management, Open Data, Historical Data, and Processing system:

- FIWARE ORION Context Broker (see section 4.3) as Publish/Subscribe system which is able to handle context information using the FIWARE NGSI standard;
- FIWARE Cygnus (see section 4.4) as connector system which persists FIWARE Orion context information in the CKAN Open Data system;
- CKAN (see section 4.7) as Open Data system to publish, share, find, use and visualize datasets of interest for the Waste4Think project such as socio-economic data, geographic information or sensors data.
- InfluxDB (see section 4.6) as Historical DB;
- CEP Sandwich (see section 4.5) as Complex Event Processing system;
- CRUD (see section 4.9) as custom tool which provides a WEB interface to create, update and delete data available both in the FIWARE Orion Context Broker and the Historical DB.
- Admin Back-End (see section 4.8) as custom tool for authenticating and authorizing users to access each of the different applications developed in the Waste4Think project (Social Actions, Zero Waste Ecosystems, Planning Tool, Green Procurement, etc.).

4.2. Deployment approach

Waste4Think Back-End components have been deployed by using Docker technology.

Docker is a software containerisation platform guaranteeing that software will always run the same, regardless of its environment. Docker offers many benefits over traditional application deployment, including:

- Simplicity – Once an application is Dockerized, a full control (start, stop, restart, etc.) with few commands is provided. As these are generic Docker commands, it is easy for anyone unfamiliar with the specifics of an application to get started.
- It's already Dockerized – Docker Hub is the central marketplace for Docker images to be shared with other Docker users. Often Docker images for an application already exist. A specific Waste4Think organization has been created into the official Docker HUB in order to store and distribute the container images created for the Waste4Think project <https://hub.docker.com/u/waste4think/dashboard/> (see Figure 14).

Repository Name	Stars	Pulls	Action
waste4think/ngsi-connector	0	11	DETAILS
waste4think/ngsi-connector-web	0	11	DETAILS
waste4think/fiware-idm	0	4	DETAILS
waste4think/authzforce	0	3	DETAILS
waste4think/pep_proxy	0	2	DETAILS

Figure 14 - Waste4Think organization in Docker HUB

- Blueprint of application configuration – A Docker file provides the blueprint or instructions to build an application. This can be stored in the source version control system and refined over time to improve the build. It also removes any ambiguity of build/configuration differences between various deployments.

The back-end services have been deployed by using the Docker-Compose which is a tool for defining and running multi-container Docker applications. With Docker-Compose, a set of YAML configuration files have been created to configure the Waste4Think services.

More details about Docker can be found in the [Annex A - Docker manual](#) of this deliverable.

4.3. FIWARE Orion Context Broker

4.3.1. Service overall description

Orion Context Broker is a C++ implementation of the NGSIv2 REST API [24] binding developed as a part of the FIWARE platform. Orion Context Broker handles the entire lifecycle of context information including updates, queries, registrations, and subscriptions. It is an NGSIv2 server implementation to manage context information and its availability. Orion Context Broker allows to create context elements and to manage them through updates and queries. In addition, external services are allowed to subscribe to context information so when an attribute of the context elements changes the subscribers receive a notification through an NGSI context update message.

As part of the Waste4Think Backend, the Orion Context Broker has been implemented to:

- manage all NGSI context information compliant to the Data Model defined in the Waste4Think project (section 7 of the D2.1 [3]), coming from Pilots and other Backend services;
- notify context information changes to other Backend services as CEP system (see section 4.5 of this deliverable), Open Data system (see section 4.7 of this deliverable) or Historical DB (see section 4.6 of this deliverable) by configuring specific subscriptions;
- retrieve, upload and update context information directly in the Orion Context Broker by using NGSI v2 APIs[24].

4.3.2. Source code repository

The official FIWARE Orion Context Broker source code repository is being hosted on GITHUB at the following link <https://github.com/telefonicaid/fiware-orion> .

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is being hosted on DOCKER Hub at the following link <https://hub.docker.com/r/fiware/orion/> .

The official MongoDB source code repository is being hosted on GITHUB at the following link <https://github.com/mongodb/mongo>.

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is being hosted on DOCKER Hub at the following link https://hub.docker.com/_/mongo/.

4.3.3. Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think project, FIWARE Orion Context broker has been deployed by using Docker technologies.

Just to mention, there are additional ways to deploy the FIWARE Orion service. More information on the different deployment options can be found in the official FIWARE Orion Context Broker Installation & Administration Manual [13].

Two different ways can be used to deploy the Orion Context Broker by using Docker.

- Installation by using docker cli command;
- Installation by using docker-compose.

Docker cli method

MongoDB installation.

```
➤ docker run -name < container name > mongodb -d mongo:3.4
```

The MongoDB container will run on the default port 27107.

FIWARE Orion installation.

```
➤ docker run -d --name <orion name> --link mongodb:mongodb -p 1026:1026  
fiware/orion -dbhost mongodb
```

FIWARE Orion container will run on port 1026.

Docker-compose method

In the Table 3 the docker-compose.yml file used to deploy the FIWARE Orion instance in the Waste4Think Back-End environment. It creates two docker containers, FIWARE Orion Context Broker and MongoDB, and defines volumes to persist data. With this approach we build a scalable application, which can be moved between any host without losing its core functionalities.

```
version: "2"

services:

  mongo:

    image: mongo:3.4

    volumes:

      - /data/docker-mongo/db:/data/db

      - /data/docker-  
mongo/log/mongodb.log:/var/log/mongodb/mongod.log

    command: --nojournal

  orion:

    image: fiware/orion

    volumes:

      - /data/docker-  
mongo/log/contextBroker.log:/tmp/contextBroker.log

      - /data/docker-mongo/config/localhost.key:/localhost.key

      - /data/docker-mongo/config/localhost.pem:/localhost.pem

    links:

      - mongo

    ports:

      - "1026:1026"
```

```

command: -dbhost mongo -https -key /localhost.key -cert
/localhost.pem -logLevel DEBUG

networks:

  default:

    driver: bridge

    driver_opts:

      com.docker.network.driver.mtu: 1400

```

Table 3 – Orion docker compose file

Two services have been configured in the docker compose file, MongoDB and FIWARE Orion.

MongoDB

Image: The MongoDB docker image version 3.4 has been used as recommended in the official FIWARE Orion documentation (see Table 4).

```
image: mongo:3.4
```

Table 4 – MongoDB docker image

Volumes: Data is non-persistent in the dockerized Orion instance. This means that turning off the MongoDB container all data will be lost. To make the MongoDB data persistent, a docker volume has been created in the docker-compose file. This volume maps the MongoDB data to an external folder located to the host system (see Table 5).

```

volumes:

  - /data/docker-mongo/db:/data/db

```

Table 5 – MongoDB docker volumes (data persistent)

The docker volume has been also used to map the MongoDB log file to an external folder (see Table 6).

```
- /data/docker-mongo/log/mongodb.log:/var/log/mongodb/mongod.log
```

Table 6 – MongoDB docker volumes (logs)

Command: The “—nojournal” command has been defined to disable journaling that MongoDB enables by default (see Table 7).

```
command: --nojournal
```

Table 7 – MongoDB docker commands

Orion Context Broker

Image: The last version of the official FIWARE Orion on Docker hub (see Table 8).

```
image: fiware/orion
```

Table 8 – Orion docker image

Volumes: A docker volume has been created to map the Orion Context Broker log to an external folder (see Table 9).

```
- /data/docker-mongo/log/contextBroker.log:/tmp/contextBroker.log
```

Table 9 – Orion docker volumes (logs)

The docker volumes have been also used to map the Orion certificates (.key and .pem) used to run Orion in HTTPS mode (see Table 10).

```
- /data/docker-mongo/config/localhost.key:/localhost.key
- /data/docker-mongo/config/localhost.pem:/localhost.pem
```

Table 10 – Orion docker volumes (certificates)

Links: Link to mongoDB service (see Table 11).

```
links:
  - mongo
```

Table 11 – Orion docker links

Ports: This setup ports on which service will run. The default Orion port 1026 has been used in the Waste4Think backend (see Table 12).

```
ports:
  - "1026:1026"
```

Table 12 – Orion docker ports

Command: Command options used when the container is created (see Table 13).

The *-dbhost* configures the MongoDB database used by FIWARE Orion.

The *-https* configures FIWARE Orion to run in HTTPS mode, which in addition needs the *-key* and *-cert* options, to specify the files containing the private key and certificates for the server.

The *-logLevel* configures the Orion log level.

```
command: -dbhost mongo -https -key /localhost.key -cert
/localhost.pem -logLevel
```

4.3.4. Manage FIWARE Orion Context Broker Service

Start service: `docker-compose up`.

Stop service: `docker-compose stop`.

Monitoring live state of FIWARE Orion: `docker stats`.

Access to the container of FIWARE Orion: `docker exec -it <fiware-orion-container> bash`.

4.3.5. Interaction with other back-end components

FIWARE Orion interacts with other back-end components:

- FIWARE Cygnus, to publish context information into the Open Data Platform CKAN;
- Time series DB InfluxDB, to upload context information as Historical Data;
- CEP-Sandwich module, to process and analyse real-time events and to trigger instantaneous predefined actions;

The interaction between FIWARE Orion and the other back-end components takes place through the configuration of FIWARE Orion subscriptions to notify context information to other services. More details about the FIWARE Orion subscriptions implemented to notify entities to FIWARE Cygnus, InfluxDB and CEP, can be found in the [Annex B – FIWARE Orion subscriptions](#)

4.4. FIWARE Cygnus Connector Framework

4.4.1. Service overall description

FIWARE Cygnus is a connector in charge of persisting Orion context data in certain configured third-party storages, creating a historical view of such data.

Internally, Cygnus is based on Apache Flume [16], a technology addressing the design and execution of data collection and persistence agents. An agent is basically composed of a listener or source in charge of receiving the data, a channel where the source puts the data once it has been transformed into a Flume event, and a sink, which takes Flume events from the channel to persist the data within its body into a third-party storage.

Cygnus and more specifically the Cygnus-NGSI agent plays the role of a connector between Orion Context Broker which is an NGSI source of data, and many FIWARE and third-party storage systems such as CKAN [14], Cosmos Big Data (Hadoop)[17] and STH Comet[18].

As part of the Waste4Think Back-end, Cygnus has been implemented to accept NGSI context information coming from Orion Context Broker and to write it to the Waste4Think CKAN Open Data Platform (see section 4.7).

4.4.2. Source code repository

The official FIWARE Cygnus source code repository is being hosted on GITHUB at the following link <https://github.com/telefonicaid/fiware-cygnus>.

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is being hosted on DOCKER Hub at the following link <https://hub.docker.com/r/fiware/cygnus-ngsi/>.

4.4.3. Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think context, FIWARE Cygnus has been deployed using the docker-compose method.

There are also other different ways to deploy FIWARE Cygnus. More information on that can be found in the official FIWARE Cygnus Installation & Administration Manual [6].

Docker-compose method

In the Table 14 the docker-compose file used to deploy the FIWARE Cygnus instance in the Waste4Think Back-End environment is presented.

```
version: '3'

services:
  cygnus:
    image: telefonicaid/fiware-cygnus
    volumes:
      - /data/docker_cygnus/conf/agent_w4t.conf:/opt/apache-flume/conf/agent.conf
      - /data/docker_cygnus/conf/name_mappings.conf:/usr/cygnus/conf/name_mappings.conf
      - /data/docker_cygnus/conf/cygnus_instance_w4t.conf:/opt/fiware-cygnus/cygnus-common/conf/cygnus_instance.conf
      - /data/docker_cygnus/log/cygnus.log:/var/log/cygnus/cygnus.log
    ports:
      - "5050:5050"
      - "8081:8081"
  networks:
    default:
      driver: bridge
      driver_opts:
        com.docker.network.driver.mtu: 1400
```

Table 14 – Cygnus docker compose file

The Cygnus image used service of the docker-compose file use the official Cygnus image.

Mapping volumes helps to configure the behaviour of Cygnus, mostly focus on key areas such as name mappings, agent configuration, and Cygnus instance.

Name mappings to determine the way of handling entities from incoming notifications, specify setting parameters like destination CKAN data store and format in which entities are being persisted. There is another counterpart which can be used that is Grouping rules, but since Cygnus version 1.6 that feature is deprecated in favour of name mappings.

Agent configuration file is used to set channel, source and sink specific settings. Only the CKAN sink has been configured in the Waste4Think project.

Files mentioned above are part of Cygnus configuration. They are required for key Cygnus aspects such as sinks on which data received from notification will be sent, the behaviour of those sinks regulated with channels options as well Cygnus instance settings (port, default service, and service path and notification endpoint).

Cygnus configuration files used in Waste4Think back-end environment are as follows:

- Agent configuration file *<agent_w4t.conf>*;
- Cygnus instance configuration file *<cygnus_instance_w4t.conf>*;
- Name mappings configuration file *<name_mappings.conf >*.

Agent configuration file

Figure 15 - Cygnus agent

The Agent configuration file is used to address Flume[16] parameters [16], configuring the source (NGSI), the channel and the sink (CKAN) that compose the Flume agent [16] behind Cygnus instance, which is responsible for consuming context events notified by the FIWARE Orion Context Broker and persisting them on the CKAN instance (see Figure 15).

The Agent configuration file can be split into two main parts:

- NGSI source configuration;
- CKAN sink configuration.

NGSI source configuration

In Table 15 the NGSI source configuration of the Flume agent. This part of Agent configuration file defines the port on which Cygnus will receive the event notified by the

Context Broker, the default service and the service path used for data persistence into the CKAN instance as well as the name mappings file used to determine the style of data that will be written in the CKAN instance.

```

cygnus-ngsi.sources = http-source
cygnus-ngsi.sinks = ckan-sink
cygnus-ngsi.channels = ckan-channel
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.channels = ckan-channel
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.type = http
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.port = 5050
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.handler =
com.telefonica.iot.cygnus.handlers.NGSIRestHandler
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.handler.notification_target = /notify
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.handler.default_service =
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.handler.default_service_path = /
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.handler.events_ttl = 10
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.interceptors = ts nmi
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.interceptors.ts.type = timestamp
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.interceptors.nmi.type =
com.telefonica.iot.cygnus.interceptors.NGSINameMappingsInterceptor$Builder
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.interceptors.nmi.name_mappings_conf_file =
/usr/cygnus/conf/name_mappings.conf

```

Table 15 - Agent configuration file NGSI configuration section.

```
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.port = 5050
```

Listening port that FIWARE Cygnus source is using for receiving incoming notifications.

```
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.handler.notification_target = /notify
```

Endpoint on which FIWARE Cygnus is listening for incoming notifications.

```
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.handler.default_service =
```

```
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.handler.default_service_path = /
```

Fiware-Service and Fiware-ServicePath default configuration.

```
cygnus-ngsi.sources.http-source.interceptors.nmi.name_mappings_conf_file =
/opt/apache-flume/conf/name_mappings.conf
```

Path of the name_mappings.conf file.

CKAN sink configuration

In Table 16 the CKAN sink configuration of the Flume agent. This part of Agent configuration file defines the CKAN parameters which are being used by Cygnus to persist data into. These settings determine how data will be written (row or column), specific connection rules, times, CKAN endpoint, port and API key (used to authenticate Cygnus when making requests to CKAN endpoint).

```
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.type =
com.telefonica.iot.cygnus.sinks.NGSICKANSink

cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.channel = ckan-channel

cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.enable_encoding = false
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.enable_grouping = false
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.enable_name_mappings = true
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.data_model = dm-by-entity
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.attr_persistence = column
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.ckan_host = 192.168.216.171
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.ckan_port = 8080
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.ckan_viewer = recline_grid_view
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.ssl = false

cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.api_key = 2d63e69c-9829-4b86-a921-
60de39750253

cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.orion_url = http://localhost:1026
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.batch_size = 100
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.batch_timeout = 30
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.batch_ttl = 10
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.batch_retry_intervals = 5000
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.backend.max_conns = 500
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.backend.max_conns_per_route = 100
#cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.persistence_policy.max_records = 5
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.persistence_policy.expiration_time = -1
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.persistence_policy.checking_time = 600
```

Table 16 - Agent configuration file CKAN configuration section.

```
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.enable_name_mappings = true
```

Enables name mappings rules for CKAN sinks, these rules are then used to customize the operations of persisting data into CKAN.

```
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.api_key = 2d63e69c-9829-4b86-a921-60de39750253
```

CKAN API key, used by Cygnus to authenticate itself when making a request to CKAN.

```
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.orion_url = http://localhost:1026
```

FIWARE Orion URL used to compose the resource URL with the convenience operation URL to query it.

```
cygnus-ngsi.sinks.ckan-sink.ckan_port = 8080
```

The port for the CKAN API endpoint.

Cygnus instance configuration file

Table 17 presents the Cygnus instance configuration file which addresses all none-Flume parameters, such as the Flume agent name, the specific log file for this instance, the administration port.

```
CYGNUS_USER=cygnus
CONFIG_FOLDER=/usr/cygnus/conf
CONFIG_FILE=/usr/cygnus/conf/agent_w4t.conf
AGENT_NAME=cygnus-ngsi
LOGFILE_NAME=cygnus.log
ADMIN_PORT=8081
POLLING_INTERVAL=30
```

Table 17 - Cygnus instance configuration file

```
CONFIG_FILE=/usr/cygnus/conf/agent_w4t.conf
```

Name of the agent. The name of the agent is important since it is the base for the Flume parameters naming conventions, it suggests what agent configuration will be used for configuration of Flume environment.

Name mappings configuration file

In Table 18 a part of “*name_mappings.conf*” file used for the purpose of customizing the way of writing data to the CKAN instance. The whole configuration file used in the Waste4Think Project can be found in the [Annex D – Cygnus Name Mappings](#) of this document.

Name mappings are an advanced global feature of Cygnus. It is global because it is available for all NGSI sinks. They allow changing the notified FIWARE service path and the concatenation of the entity ID and entity type.

```
{
  "serviceMappings": [
    {
      "originalService": "waste4think",
      "servicePathMappings": [
        {
          "originalServicePath": "/deusto/w4t/cascais/real",
          "entityMappings": [
            {
              "originalEntityId": ".*",
              "originalEntityType": "DepositPointType",
              "newEntityId": "",
              "newEntityType": "depositpointtype",
              "attributeMappings": []
            },
            {
              "originalEntityId": ".*",
              "originalEntityType": "SortingType",
              "newEntityId": "",
              "newEntityType": "sortingtype",
              "attributeMappings": []
            },
            {
              "originalEntityId": ".*",
              "originalEntityType": "DepositPointIsle",
              "newEntityId": "",
              "newEntityType": "depositpointisle",
              "attributeMappings": []
            },
            {
              "originalEntityId": ".*",
              "originalEntityType": "DepositPoint",
```

```

        "newEntityId": "",
        "newEntityType": "depositpoint",
        "attributeMappings": []
    },
]
},
...

```

Table 18 – Name mappings configuration file

originalService: Fiware Orion service from incoming notification, used to map incoming request to set of rules for that specific service.

originalServicePath: Fiware Orion service path from incoming notification used to map set of rules that are specific to service path, allowing us distinction of entities depending on their service path rather than attributes (id, type ...).

originalEntityId: ID of single entity, also unique to Fiware Service and Fiware ServicePath.

originalEntityType: Type of incoming entity, also unique to Fiware Service and Fiware ServicePath.

newEntityId: Used to specify a new value for each entity ID, which is then used for sending data into CKAN sink by concatenating *<newEntityId_newEntityType>*, that value will represent destination of CKAN data store which holds data specific to given resources.

nwEntityType: Used to specify a new value for each entity Type, which is then used for sending data into CKAN sink by concatenating *<newEntityId_newEntityType>*, that value will represent destination of CKAN data store which holds data specific to given resources.

4.5. CEP

4.5.1. Service overall description

The CEP module (named as Sandwich) is an application to trigger logic at the occurrence of certain events. Its purpose is to build small programs (called sandwiches) in an interactive way by dragging and dropping already predefined functions (called ingredients). These functions are linked to determine whose outputs need to be sent to others' inputs and create the logical order in which information must flow. Combining the ingredients, a user can build (in a visual way) logical and mathematical operations to perform complex calculations (such as the mean attribute of a group of entities, execute a statistical model, etc.).

By using the Context Broker's subscription mechanism, the sandwiches can be invoked whenever an entity is changed. The CEP module will asynchronously launch the sandwich executing in sequence all its ingredients and after, sending the result back to the Context Broker or to another module. In the background, the CEP module is built using a NodeJS web server[20] coupled with a PostgreSQL[21] database. NodeJS exposes the API routes and dispatches the received queries into the database.

4.5.2. Source code repository

The official CEP-Sandwich repository is available at <http://dev.waste4think.eu/waste4think/w4t-sandwich.git>.

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is being hosted on DOCKER Hub at <https://hub.docker.com/u/waste4think/>.

4.5.3. Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think context, the CEP-Sandwich module has been deployed by using Docker technologies, specifically by using the docker-compose method.

- To run the module:
docker stack deploy -c sandwich/docker.yml sandwich
- The logs will be available at /var/log/sandwich
- To stop the module:
docker stop sandwich

Table 19 and Table 20 show the docker.yml configuration file and the NGINX configuration of the CEP-Sandwich module.

```
version: "3"

services:
  sandwich-postgresql-db:
    image: postgres:9.6
    ports:
      - "9041:5432"
    volumes:
      - postgresql_data:/var/lib/postgresql/data
    environment:
      POSTGRES_USER: "postgres"
      POSTGRES_PASSWORD: "7f650369fa13fd4fe07e0a8e19f16ae7"
      POSTGRES_DB: "sandwich"
```

```

sandwich-pgadmin4:
  image: dpage/pgadmin4
  ports:
    - "8031:5050"
  environment:
    PGADMIN_DEFAULT_EMAIL: "pg@deusto.io"
    PGADMIN_DEFAULT_PASSWORD:
"7f650369fa13fd4fe07e0a8e19f16ae7"
    PGADMIN_ENABLE_TLS: "False"
    PGADMIN_SERVER_NAME: "sandwich-postgresql-db"

sandwich-node:
  image: "node:8"
  ports:
    - "8030:8030"
  environment:
    POSTGRES_USER: "postgres"
    POSTGRES_PASSWORD: "7f650369fa13fd4fe07e0a8e19f16ae7"
    POSTGRES_HOST: "sandwich-postgresql-db"
    POSTGRES_PORT: 5432
    POSTGRES_DB: "sandwich"
  user: "node"
  working_dir: /home/ander/sandwich
  volumes:
    - /home/ander/sandwich:/home/ander/sandwich
  command: /bin/bash -c "npm start"
  dns:
    - 130.206.100.1
    - 130.206.100.2

volumes:
  postgresql_data:

```

Table 19 – Docker compose file of the CEP-Sandwich module

```

server {
  server_name sandwich.waste4think.com;

```

```
listen 80;

listen 443 ssl;

include conf.d/geoworldsim_ssl;

location / {
    proxy_pass_header Server;
    proxy_set_header Host $http_host;
    proxy_redirect off;
    proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;
    proxy_set_header X-Scheme $scheme;
    proxy_connect_timeout 120s;
    proxy_send_timeout 120s;
    proxy_read_timeout 120s;
    proxy_pass http://192.168.235.170:8030;
}
}
```

Table 20 – Nginx configuration file for the CEP-Sandwich module

4.6. History module

4.6.1. Service overall description

The Historical module contains a time-series database that stores the entire temporality of an entity. Its purpose is to be subscribed to every Context Broker entity to monitor and keep track of their changes. Whenever an entity is modified, the Context Broker will emit a POST to the Historical module, and this last will create a new time record with when the entity was changed and its new value.

Using the stored data, the module exposes an API for querying past states the entities had in the Context Broker given a timestamp or time range. In the background, the Historical module is built using a NodeJS[20] web server coupled with an InfluxDB[23] time-series database. NodeJS exposes the API routes and dispatches the received queries into the database.

4.6.2. Source code repository

The official Historical module source code repository is available at: <http://dev.waste4think.eu/waste4think/w4t-history.git>.

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is being hosted on DOCKER Hub at <https://hub.docker.com/u/waste4think/>.

4.6.3. Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think context, the Historical module has been deployed by using Docker technologies, specifically by using the docker-compose method.

- To run the module:
docker stack deploy -c history/docker.yml history
- The logs will be available at /var/log/history
- To stop the module:
docker stop history

Table 21 shows the Docker compose configuration file of the History module. Table 22 shows the Nginx configuration file for the History module.

```
version: "3"
services:
  history-influx-db:
    image: influxdb:1.3
    volumes:
      - influx_data:/var/lib/influxdb

  history-node:
    image: "node:8"
    ports:
      - "8040:8040" #history.deusto.io
    environment:
      INFLUX_HOST: "history-influx-db"
      INFLUX_PORT: "8086"
    user: "node"
    working_dir: /home/ander/history
    volumes:
      - /home/ander/history:/home/ander/history
    command: /bin/bash -c "npm start"
    dns:
      - 130.206.100.1
      - 130.206.100.2

volumes:
  influx_data:
```

Table 21 – Docker compose file for the History module

```
server {
  server_name history.waste4think.com;
  listen 443 ssl;
  listen 80;

  include conf.d/geoworldsim_ssl;

  location / {
    proxy_pass_header Server;
    proxy_set_header Host $http_host;
    proxy_redirect off;
    proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;
```

```

proxy_set_header X-Scheme $scheme;
proxy_connect_timeout 120s;
proxy_send_timeout 120s;
proxy_read_timeout 120s;
proxy_pass http://192.168.235.170:8040/;
}
}

```

Table 22 – Nginx configuration file for the History module

4.7. CKAN Open Data

4.7.1. Service overall description

CKAN is a tool for making open data websites. It helps manage and publish collections of data. It is used by national and local governments, research institutions, and other organizations who collect a lot of data.

Once data is published, users can use its faceted search features to browse and find the data they need, and preview it using maps, graphs and tables-whether they are developers, journalists, researchers, NGOs, citizens, etc....

As part of the Waste4Think Back-End, the open data platform CKAN is used to publish, share, find, use and visualize datasets of interest for the Waste4Think project such as socio-economic data, geographic information or sensors data.

In the Waste4Think context, a private instance of CKAN (see Figure 16) has been deployed and configured. It is running at the following link:

<http://backend.waste4think.eu:8080/>.

Figure 16 - W4T CKAN

4.7.2. Source code repository

The official CKAN source code repository is being hosted on GITHUB at the following link <https://github.com/ckan/ckan>.

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is being hosted on DOCKER Hub at the following link <https://hub.docker.com/r/ckan/ckan/>.

4.7.3. Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think project, the CKAN instance has been deployed by using Docker technologies.

There are different methods to install CKAN as the installation from an operating system package manager or from source. More information about it can be found in the official CKAN documentation [14].

Docker-compose method

In the Table 3 the docker-compose.yml file used to deploy the CKAN instance in the Waste4Think Backend environment is presented.

```
volumes:

  ckan_config:

  ckan_home:

  ckan_storage:

  pg_data:

services:

  ckan:

    container_name: ckan

    build:

      context: ../../

      args:

        - CKAN_SITE_URL=${CKAN_SITE_URL}

    links:

      - db

      - solr

      - redis

    ports:

      - "0.0.0.0:${CKAN_PORT}:5000"

    environment:
```

```
# Defaults work with linked containers, change to use own Postgres,
Solr, Redis or Datapusher

-
CKAN_SQLALCHEMY_URL=postgresql://ckan:${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}@db/ckan

-
CKAN_DATASTORE_WRITE_URL=postgresql://ckan:${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}@datastore

-
CKAN_DATASTORE_READ_URL=postgresql://datastore_ro:${DATASTORE_READONLY_PASSWORD}@db/datastore

- CKAN_SOLR_URL=http://solr:8983/solr/ckan
- CKAN_REDIS_URL=redis://redis:6379/1
- CKAN_DATAPUSHER_URL=http://datapusher:8800
- CKAN_SITE_URL=${CKAN_SITE_URL}
- CKAN_MAX_UPLOAD_SIZE_MB=${CKAN_MAX_UPLOAD_SIZE_MB}
- POSTGRES_PASSWORD=${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}
- DS_RO_PASS=${DATASTORE_READONLY_PASSWORD}

volumes:

- ckan_config:/etc/ckan
- ckan_home:/usr/lib/ckan
- ckan_storage:/var/lib/ckan

datapusher:

  container_name: datapusher
  image: clementmouchet/datapusher
  ports:
    - "8800:8800"

db:

  container_name: db

  build:

    context: ../../

    dockerfile: contrib/docker/postgresql/Dockerfile

  args:
```

```

- DS_RO_PASS=${DATASTORE_READONLY_PASSWORD}

- POSTGRES_PASSWORD=${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}

environment:

- DS_RO_PASS=${DATASTORE_READONLY_PASSWORD}

- POSTGRES_PASSWORD=${POSTGRES_PASSWORD}

volumes:

- pg_data:/var/lib/postgresql/data

solr:

  container_name: solr

  build:

    context: ../../

    dockerfile: contrib/docker/solr/Dockerfile

redis:

  container_name: redis

  image: redis:latest

```

Table 23 - CKAN docker compose file

```

volumes:

- ckan_config:/etc/ckan

- ckan_home:/usr/lib/ckan

- ckan_storage:/var/lib/ckan

```

Table 24 - CKAN docker volumes

Docker volumes have been used to map the CKAN configuration files and to persist data on external folders. This makes sure data is persisted and limit the risk of data lost due to issues that can occur in work with containers (see Table 24).

```

solr:

redis:

db:

datapusher:

```

Table 25 - CKAN docker dependencies

CKAN dependencies, main task of which is data management/persistence, in general, they are responsible for CKAN data flow. They handle received data but also write and manage internal CKAN data structures (see Table 25).

```
ports:
  - "0.0.0.0:${CKAN_PORT}:5000"
```

Table 26 - CKAN docker port

Port used to set endpoint of CKAN service (see Table 26).

4.8. Admin backend

4.8.1. Service overall description

The Admin backend provides a unique entry point to the Waste4Think ecosystem. Based on OAuth, this module is responsible for authenticating and authorizing users to access each of the different applications in Waste4Think: Social Actions, Zero Waste Ecosystems, Planning Tool, Green Procurement, etc.

On the registry, each user is given a role and a set of permissions that detail which application and which actions within each application the user is permitted to interact with. On log in, the Admin backend verifies the credentials of the user and returns a cross-navigation bar with all the necessary links and actions of the allowed application. This cross-navigation bar will be available in all the applications during the user session and will verify all the operations performed by them.

4.8.2. Source code repository

The official Admin backend module source code repository is available at: <http://dev.waste4think.eu/waste4think/w4t-authservice.git>.

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is being hosted on DOCKER Hub at <https://hub.docker.com/u/waste4think/>.

4.8.3. Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think context, the Admin backend module has been deployed by using Docker technologies, specifically by using the docker-compose method through the docker-remote scripts that manage all the configuration of the docker containers.

- To run the module depending on the desired environment:
docker-remote release-deploy config/development
docker-remote release-deploy config/production
- The logs will be available at /var/log/\${STACK}
- To stop the module:
docker stop /\${STACK}

Regardless of deploying either in the development or production environment, the Admin Backend requires three types of files:

- **Deployment properties file:** Configures parameters such as the host/port where the Admin backend docker container will be deployed, the docker registry to which the Admin backend image will be uploaded to, and the names of the stack, image and tag related to the container.
- **Application properties file:** Configures parameters relevant to the application, such as the users and passwords of the application and the database, logs, static and media folders, etc.
- **Docker compose file:** Configures the parameters for building the docker container.

Table 27, Table 28, and Table 29 show the configuration files to deploy the Admin Backend in the development environment. Table 30, Table 31, and Table 32 show the configuration files to deploy the Admin Backend in the production environment. Table 33 shows the Nginx configuration file for the Admin Backend.

```
HOST= 10.32.8.203
PORT=22
REGISTRY=10.32.8.203:5000
STACK=w4t_admin_dev
IMAGE=w4t_admin
TAG=dev
```

Table 27 – Deployment properties for the Admin backend module (development)

```
DJANGO_SECRET_KEY= "13+cs97='w(ixk2c*!8sskfksnaf*(__c!44)$1b(v0ejci"
DJANGO_ALLOWED_HOSTS=admin-dev.waste4think.com
DJANGO_HOST_PORT=8011
DJANGO_DEBUG=True

DJANGO_ADMIN_USER=w4t_user
DJANGO_ADMIN_PASSWORD=#DJANGO_ADMIN_PASS#
DJANGO_ADMIN_EMAIL=#DJANGO_ADMIN_EMAIL#

DJANGO_STATIC_URL=/static/
DJANGO_STATIC_ROOT=/var/www/static
DJANGO_STATIC_HOST_PATH=/var/www/${STACK}/static
DJANGO_MEDIA_URL=/media/
DJANGO_MEDIA_ROOT=/var/www/media
DJANGO_MEDIA_HOST_PATH=/var/www/${STACK}/media

DJANGO_GUNICORN_LOG=/var/log/${STACK}/gunicorn
DJANGO_GUNICORN_NAME=${STACK}

POSTGRES_HOST=postgres
POSTGRES_PORT=5432
POSTGRES_DB_NAME=${STACK}_db
POSTGRES_USER=w4t_user
POSTGRES_PASSWORD=#POSTGRES_PASS#
POSTGRES_HOST_PORT=8013
POSTGRES_DATA=/var/postgres/${STACK}
```

Table 28 – Application properties for the Admin backend module (development)

```
version: '3.1'
services:
```

```

django:
  image: '${REGISTRY}/${IMAGE}:${TAG}'
  ports:
    - ${DJANGO_HOST_PORT}:8000
  env_file:
    - ${STACK}.env
  depends_on:
    - postgres
  volumes:
    - ${DJANGO_STATIC_HOST_PATH}:${DJANGO_STATIC_ROOT}
    - ${DJANGO_MEDIA_HOST_PATH}:${DJANGO_MEDIA_ROOT}
    - ${DJANGO_GUNICORN_LOG}:/var/log/gunicorn

postgres:
  image: postgres:10
  ports:
    - ${POSTGRES_HOST_PORT}:${POSTGRES_PORT}
  env_file:
    - ${STACK}.env
  volumes:
    - ${POSTGRES_DATA}:/var/lib/postgresql/data

```

Table 29 – Docker compose file for the Admin backend module (development)

```

HOST= 192.168.235.170
PORT=22
REGISTRY= https://hub.docker.com/u/waste4think/
STACK=w4t_admin
IMAGE=w4t_admin
TAG=latest

```

Table 30 – Deployment properties for the Admin backend module (production)

```

DJANGO_SECRET_KEY= "13+cs97='w(kvvnvdj764jsad*(__c!44)$1b(v0efsd"
DJANGO_ALLOWED_HOSTS=admin.waste4think.com
DJANGO_HOST_PORT=8010
DJANGO_DEBUG=False

DJANGO_ADMIN_USER=w4t_user
DJANGO_ADMIN_PASSWORD=#DJANGO_ADMIN_PASS#
DJANGO_ADMIN_EMAIL=#DJANGO_ADMIN_EMAIL#

DJANGO_STATIC_URL=/static/
DJANGO_STATIC_ROOT=/var/www/static
DJANGO_STATIC_HOST_PATH=/var/www/${STACK}/static
DJANGO_MEDIA_URL=/media/
DJANGO_MEDIA_ROOT=/var/www/media
DJANGO_MEDIA_HOST_PATH=/var/www/${STACK}/media

DJANGO_GUNICORN_LOG=/var/log/${STACK}/gunicorn
DJANGO_GUNICORN_NAME=${STACK}

POSTGRES_HOST=postgres
POSTGRES_PORT=5432
POSTGRES_DB_NAME=${STACK}_db
POSTGRES_USER=w4t_user
POSTGRES_PASSWORD=#PROD_POSTGRES_PASS#
POSTGRES_DATA=/var/postgres/${STACK}

```

Table 31 – Application properties for the Admin backend module (production)

```

version: '3.1'

```

```

services:
  django:
    image: '${REGISTRY}/${IMAGE}:${TAG}'
    ports:
      - ${DJANGO_HOST_PORT}:8000
    env_file:
      - ${STACK}.env
    depends_on:
      - postgres
    volumes:
      - ${DJANGO_STATIC_HOST_PATH}:${DJANGO_STATIC_ROOT}
      - ${DJANGO_MEDIA_HOST_PATH}:${DJANGO_MEDIA_ROOT}
      - ${DJANGO_GUNICORN_LOG}:/var/log/gunicorn

  postgres:
    image: postgres:10
    ports:
      - ${POSTGRES_HOST_PORT}:${POSTGRES_PORT}
    env_file:
      - ${STACK}.env
    volumes:
      - ${POSTGRES_DATA}:/var/lib/postgresql/data

```

Table 32 – Docker compose file for the Admin backend module (production)

```

server {
    server_name auth.waste4think.com;
    listen 443 ssl;

    error_log /var/log/nginx/error.log debug;
    rewrite_log on;

    location /static/ {
        alias /var/www/w4t_authservice/static/;
    }

    location /media/ {
        alias /var/www/w4t_authservice/media/;
    }

    location / {
        proxy_pass_header Server;
        proxy_set_header Host $http_host;
        proxy_redirect off;
        proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;
        proxy_set_header X-Scheme $scheme;
        proxy_connect_timeout 120s;
        proxy_send_timeout 120s;
        proxy_read_timeout 120s;
        proxy_pass http://192.168.235.170:8010/;
    }
}

server {
    server_name auth-dev.waste4think.com;
    listen 443 ssl;

    location /static/ {
        alias /var/www/w4t_authservice/static/;
    }

    location /media/ {
        alias /var/www/w4t_authservice/media/;
    }

    location / {

```

```

proxy_pass_header Server;
proxy_set_header Host $http_host;
proxy_redirect off;
proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;
proxy_set_header X-Scheme $scheme;
proxy_connect_timeout 120s;
proxy_send_timeout 120s;
proxy_read_timeout 120s;
proxy_pass http://192.168.235.170:8011/;
}
}

```

Table 33 – Nginx file for the Admin backend module (development and production)

4.9. CRUD

4.9.1. Service overall description

The CRUD module provides a web interface for operating over the data available in the data-model. The operations available are create, update and delete. This module will be available only to the data administrators, providing them with a failsafe in case there is a misreading in any sensor or there is corruption in the data.

CRUD will provide an interface to work with both the API of the FIWARE Orion Context Broker (Section 4.3) and the History module (Section 4.6). Figure 17 shows one of the CRUD's user interface.

Figure 17 - W4T CRUD user interface

4.9.2. Source code repository

The official CRUD module source code repository is available at: <http://dev.waste4think.eu/waste4think/w4t-crud.git>

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is being hosted on DOCKER Hub at <https://hub.docker.com/u/waste4think/>

4.9.3. Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think context, the CRUD module has been deployed by using Docker technologies, specifically by using the docker-compose method through the docker-remote scripts that manage all the configuration of the docker containers.

- To run the module depending on the desired environment:
docker-remote release-deploy config/development
docker-remote release-deploy config/production
- The logs will be available at /var/log/\${STACK}
- To stop the module:
docker stop /\${STACK}

Regardless of deploying either in the development or production environment, the CRUD requires three types of files:

- **Deployment properties file:** Configures parameters such as the host/port where the Admin backend docker container will be deployed, the docker registry to which the Admin backend image will be uploaded to, and the names of the stack, image and tag related to the container.
- **Application properties file:** Configures parameters relevant to the application, such as the users and passwords of the application and the database, logs, static and media folders, etc.
- **Docker compose file:** Configures the parameters for building the docker container.

Table 34, Table 35, Table 36 show the configuration files to deploy the CRUD in the development environment. Table 37, Table 38, Table 39 show the configuration files to deploy the CRUD in the production environment. Table 33 shows the Nginx configuration file for the CRUD.

```
HOST= 10.32.8.203
PORT=22
REGISTRY=10.32.8.203:5000
STACK=w4t_crud_dev
IMAGE=w4t_crud
TAG=dev
```

Table 34 – Deployment properties for the CRUD module (development)

```
DJANGO_SECRET_KEY= " uqn&q$yr6 (fyq*!z$g8f5zc&wxna_48)x!l+orhnjpb7^3skd"
DJANGO_ALLOWED_HOSTS=crud-dev.waste4think.com
DJANGO_HOST_PORT=9081
DJANGO_DEBUG=True

DJANGO_ADMIN_USER=w4t_user
DJANGO_ADMIN_PASSWORD=#DJANGO_ADMIN_PASS#
DJANGO_ADMIN_EMAIL=#DJANGO_ADMIN_EMAIL#

DJANGO_STATIC_URL=/static/
DJANGO_STATIC_ROOT=/var/www/static
DJANGO_STATIC_HOST_PATH=/var/www/${STACK}/static
DJANGO_MEDIA_URL=/media/
DJANGO_MEDIA_ROOT=/var/www/media
DJANGO_MEDIA_HOST_PATH=/var/www/${STACK}/media
```

```
DJANGO_GUNICORN_LOG=/var/log/${STACK}/gunicorn
DJANGO_GUNICORN_NAME=${STACK}
```

```
POSTGRES_HOST=postgres
POSTGRES_PORT=5432
POSTGRES_DB_NAME=${STACK}_db
POSTGRES_USER=w4t_user
POSTGRES_PASSWORD=#POSTGRES_PASS#
POSTGRES_HOST_PORT=9083
POSTGRES_DATA=/var/postgres/${STACK}
```

Table 35 – Application properties for the CRUD module (development)

```
version: '3.1'
services:
  django:
    image: '${REGISTRY}/${IMAGE}:${TAG}'
    ports:
      - ${DJANGO_HOST_PORT}:8000
    env_file:
      - ${STACK}.env
    depends_on:
      - postgres
    volumes:
      - ${DJANGO_STATIC_HOST_PATH}:${DJANGO_STATIC_ROOT}
      - ${DJANGO_MEDIA_HOST_PATH}:${DJANGO_MEDIA_ROOT}
      - ${DJANGO_GUNICORN_LOG}:/var/log/gunicorn

  postgres:
    image: postgres:10
    ports:
      - ${POSTGRES_HOST_PORT}:${POSTGRES_PORT}
    env_file:
      - ${STACK}.env
    volumes:
      - ${POSTGRES_DATA}:/var/lib/postgresql/data
```

Table 36 – Docker compose file for the CRUD module (development)

```
HOST= 192.168.235.170
PORT=22
REGISTRY= https://hub.docker.com/u/waste4think/
STACK=w4t_crud
IMAGE=w4t_crud
TAG=latest
```

Table 37 – Deployment properties for the CRUD module (production)

```
DJANGO_SECRET_KEY= "uqn&q$yr6 (fyq*!z$g8f5zc&wxna_48)x!l+orhnjpb7^3skd"
DJANGO_ALLOWED_HOSTS=crud.waste4think.com
DJANGO_HOST_PORT= 9080
DJANGO_DEBUG=False

DJANGO_ADMIN_USER=w4t_user
DJANGO_ADMIN_PASSWORD=#DJANGO_ADMIN_PASS#
DJANGO_ADMIN_EMAIL=#DJANGO_ADMIN_EMAIL#

DJANGO_STATIC_URL=/static/
DJANGO_STATIC_ROOT=/var/www/static
DJANGO_STATIC_HOST_PATH=/var/www/${STACK}/static
DJANGO_MEDIA_URL=/media/
DJANGO_MEDIA_ROOT=/var/www/media
```

```

DJANGO_MEDIA_HOST_PATH=/var/www/${STACK}/media

DJANGO_GUNICORN_LOG=/var/log/${STACK}/gunicorn
DJANGO_GUNICORN_NAME=${STACK}

POSTGRES_HOST=postgres
POSTGRES_PORT=5432
POSTGRES_DB_NAME=${STACK}_db
POSTGRES_USER=w4t_user
POSTGRES_PASSWORD=#PROD_POSTGRES_PASS#
POSTGRES_DATA=/var/postgres/${STACK}

```

Table 38 – Application properties for the CRUD module (production)

```

version: '3.1'
services:
  django:
    image: '${REGISTRY}/${IMAGE}:${TAG}'
    ports:
      - ${DJANGO_HOST_PORT}:8000
    env_file:
      - ${STACK}.env
    depends_on:
      - postgres
    volumes:
      - ${DJANGO_STATIC_HOST_PATH}:${DJANGO_STATIC_ROOT}
      - ${DJANGO_MEDIA_HOST_PATH}:${DJANGO_MEDIA_ROOT}
      - ${DJANGO_GUNICORN_LOG}:/var/log/gunicorn

  postgres:
    image: postgres:10
    ports:
      - ${POSTGRES_HOST_PORT}:${POSTGRES_PORT}
    env_file:
      - ${STACK}.env
    volumes:
      - ${POSTGRES_DATA}:/var/lib/postgresql/data

```

Table 39 – Docker compose file for the CRUD module (production)

```

server {
    server_name crud.waste4think.com;
    listen 443 ssl;

    error_log /var/log/nginx/error.log debug;
    rewrite_log on;

    location /static/ {
        alias /var/www/w4t_crud/static/;
    }

    location /media/ {
        alias /var/www/w4t_crud/media/;
    }

    location / {
        proxy_pass_header Server;
        proxy_set_header Host $http_host;
        proxy_redirect off;
        proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;
        proxy_set_header X-Scheme $scheme;
        proxy_connect_timeout 120s;
        proxy_send_timeout 120s;
        proxy_read_timeout 120s;
    }
}

```

```

        proxy_pass http://192.168.235.170:9080/;
    }
}
server {
    server_name crud-dev.waste4think.com;
    listen 443 ssl;

    location /static/ {
        alias /var/www/w4t_crud/static/;
    }

    location /media/ {
        alias /var/www/w4t_crud/media/;
    }

    location / {
        proxy_pass_header Server;
        proxy_set_header Host $http_host;
        proxy_redirect off;
        proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;
        proxy_set_header X-Scheme $scheme;
        proxy_connect_timeout 120s;
        proxy_send_timeout 120s;
        proxy_read_timeout 120s;
        proxy_pass http://192.168.235.170:9081/;
    }
}

```

Table 40 – Nginx file for the CRUD module (development and production)

5. Security implementation

5.1. FIWARE security

The Security module implemented in the Waste4Think project manages the user account information, it authenticates the user by a FIWARE account and checks authorizations to access resources.

In the Waste4Think context, the following FIWARE Generic Enablers (see Figure 18) have been used and combined to implement secure access to the Back-End:

- The Keyrock Identity Management Generic Enabler[11] brings support to secure and private OAuth2-based[9] authentication of users and devices, user profile management, privacy-preserving disposition of personal data, Single Sign-On (SSO) and Identity Federation across multiple administration domains.
- The Wilma PEP Proxy Generic Enabler[12] brings the support of proxy functions within OAuth2-based authentication schemas. It also implements PEP functions within an XACML-based access control schema.
- The AuthZForce PDP/PAP Generic Enabler[10] brings support to PDP/PAP functions within an access control schema based on the XACML standard[19].

Figure 18 - FIWARE Security GEs

The Identity Manager (IdM) stores the FIWARE user’s account and allows Single Sign On (SSO) authentication by using the OAuth2 protocol.

Upon logging in, the user authenticated receives an authentication token which is used by the AuthZForce component to check the role of the user and permission associated.

The PEP Proxy acts as a proxy server redirecting the allowed requests or blocking the unauthorized requests (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**).

Figure 19 - W4T Back-End security layer

During the integration and test phase of the FIWARE security components in the Waste4Think back-end, it has been realized that the IDM component does not allow a user to create particular authorization permissions to HTTP resources containing a dynamic value in the URI. For instance, it is not possible to create an IDM authorization permission to the HTTP resource http://backend.waste4think.eu/v2/entities/<entity_id> where the <entity_id> is a dynamic value.

To solve this issue, it has been necessary to make changes to the source code of the PEP Proxy GE that carries out authorization checks and authorize or deny access to the back-end resources and moreover it has been necessary to define a method to create these permissions in the IDM GE.

As an example, in order to get the permission to the resource `/v2/entities/<entity_id>/attrs/<attr_id>` where `<entity_id>` and `<attr_id>` are dynamic values, from the IDM side the resource will be defined as `/v2/entities//attrs/` (see Figure 20). Therefore a new logic has been implemented in a custom version of PEP Proxy GE used in our project, to handle the permissions to this kind of resources and in particular to consider the two backslash `//` as dynamic value.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Create permission" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. The form is divided into several sections:

- Permission Name:** A text input field containing "HTTP Resource with dynamic values".
- Description:** A text input field containing "GET /v2/entities/<entity_id>/attrs/<attr_id>".
- HTTP Verb and Resource Rule:** A sub-section containing:
 - HTTP action:** A text input field containing "GET".
 - Resource:** A text input field containing "/v2/entities//attrs/".
- Advanced XACML Rule:** A section with a label and an empty text area below it.

A blue "Save" button is positioned at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 20 - IdM resource permission with dynamic values

5.2. FIWARE Wilma PEP Proxy

5.2.1. Service overall description

The Wilma PEP Proxy GE[12], playing the role of PEP (Policy Enforcement Point), is a key component to use combined with the Identity Management GE[11] and AuthZForce GE[10] that brings authentication and authorization to the back-end services. Its main functionality is to check that only the authorized FIWARE users, registered in the Waste4Think Identity Management instance (see section 5.3), are able to access the back-end resources. PEP Proxy works with OAuth2 and XACML protocols as standards for authorization and authentication in FIWARE.

The PEP Proxy is deployed on top of the back-end service, transforming the service endpoint in the PEP Proxy endpoint and redirecting the request filtered to the service. The back-end application must be registered in the IDM with OAuth2 mechanism that enables login user a FIWARE account. The OAuth2 token generated must be included in the HTTP headers sent the request to the back-end service. If the token included in the request is valid, then PEP Proxy will redirect the request to the back-end.

The WILMA PEP Proxy GE provides three levels of security as just described in the section 4.6.4 of the D2.1 [3].

- Level 1 (Authentication): PEP proxy checks if the token included in the request corresponds to an authenticated user in FIWARE IDM.
- Level 2 (Basic Authorization): PEP Proxy checks the authenticated user as defined in the Level 1 and it also checks the roles and permissions configured for that user, and allow him to access to the resource specified in the request (based in the HTTP verb + path);
- Level 3 (Advanced Authorization): PEP Proxy provides the same level security of the Level 2, so it checks user authentication, roles, and permissions with the only difference that the Level 3 use the XACML standard language to define the permissions.

In the Waste4Think project, only Level 1 and Level 2 have been considered to secure the Back-End (see Figure 21 and Figure 22).

Figure 21 - Security level 1 – Authentication

Figure 22. Security level 2 - Basic authorization

5.2.2. Source code repository

The source code of the custom version of the FIWARE PEP Proxy GE, with the changes described in section 5.1 of this deliverable, is being hosted on GITHUB at the following link <https://github.com/IgorDespot/fiware-pep-fix>.

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is the custom version of the official 6.2 version, and it is being hosted on DOCKER Hub at the following link https://hub.docker.com/r/waste4think/pep_proxy/.

5.2.3. Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think project, FIWARE PEP Proxy has been deployed by using Docker technologies.

There are different ways to deploy the FIWARE PEP Proxy GE. More information on this can be found in the official FIWARE PEP Proxy GE Installation & Administration Manual [12].

Two different ways can be used to deploy PEP Proxy by using Docker.

- Installation by using docker cli command;
- Installation by using docker-compose.

The docker-compose method has been used to deploy the PEP Proxy component in the Waste4Think context.

In the Table 41 the docker-compose.yml file used to deploy the FIWARE PEP Proxy instance in the Waste4Think Back-End environment is presented.

```
version: "3"

services:
  pep-proxy:
    image: waste4think/pep_proxy:release-6.2
    volumes:
      - /data/docker_pepproxy/conf/config.js:/opt/fiware-pep-proxy/config.js
    ports:
      - "82:82"
networks:
  default:
    driver: bridge
    driver_opts:
      com.docker.network.driver.mtu: 1400
```

Table 41 – PEP Proxy Docker compose file

Image: The PEP Proxy Docker image used is a custom version (more details can be found in the section 5.1 of this deliverable) hosted on the Waste4Think project of Docker HUB.

Volumes: Docker volumes has been created to map the configuration file of the PEP Proxy component “config.js” to an external folder.

Ports: The PEP Proxy service has been configured to run on port 82.

In the Table 42 the configuration file “config.js” used to configure the FIWARE PEP Proxy instance in the Waste4Think Back-End environment is presented.

```
config = {};  
  
// Used only if https is disabled  
  
config.pep_port = 82;  
  
// Set this var to undefined if you don't want the server to listen on  
HTTPS  
  
config.https = {  
    enabled: false,  
    cert_file: 'cert/cert.crt',  
    key_file: 'cert/key.key',  
    port: 443  
};  
  
config.account_host = 'http://192.168.229.62:8000';  
config.keystone_host = '192.168.229.62';  
config.keystone_port = 5000;  
config.app_host = '192.168.229.62';  
config.app_port = '1026';  
  
// Use true if the app server listens in https  
config.app_ssl = true;  
  
// Credentials obtained when registering PEP Proxy in Account Portal  
config.username = 'pep_proxy_1d2c28cb9dc140629efd669a36023242';  
config.password = 'f5c42df5e4304961a810417ceb5ac8b6';  
  
// in seconds  
config.cache_time = 300;  
  
// if enabled PEP checks permissions with AuthZForce GE.  
// only compatible with oauth2 tokens engine  
//  
// you can use custom policy checks by including programatic scripts  
// in policies folder. An script template is included there  
  
config.azf = {  
    enabled: false,  
    protocol: 'http',  
    host: '192.168.229.62',  
    port: 83,
```

```
    custom_policy: undefined // use undefined to default policy checks
    (HTTP verb + path).

};

// list of paths that will not check authentication/authorization
// example: ['/public/*', '/static/css/']
config.public_paths = [];

// options: oauth2/keystone
config.tokens_engine = 'oauth2';

config.magic_key = undefined;

module.exports = config;
```

Table 42 – PEP Proxy config file

5.2.4. Manage FIWARE PEP Proxy Service

Start service: docker-compose up/-d command.

Stop service: docker-compose stop command or docker stop <pep-proxy-container>.

Service logs: docker logs <pep-proxy-container>

Access to the container of FIWARE PEP Proxy: docker exec -it < pep-proxy-container> bash

5.3. FIWARE IDM – KeyRock

5.3.1. Service overall description

Identity Management covers several aspects involving users' access to networks, services, and applications, including secure and private authentication from users to devices, networks and services, authorization & trust management, user profile management, privacy-preserving disposition of personal data, Single Sign-On (SSO) to service domains and Identity Federation towards applications. The Identity Manager is the central component that provides a bridge between IDM systems at connectivity-level and application-level. Furthermore, Identity Management is used for authorizing foreign services to access personal data stored in a secure environment. Hereby usually the owner of the data must give consent to access the data; the consent-giving procedure also implies certain user authentication.

In the Waste4Think context, a private instance of FIWARE IDM (see Figure 23) has been deployed and configured. It is running at the following link:

<http://backend.waste4think.eu:8000/>.

Figure 23 - W4T IDM instance

5.3.2. Source code repository

The official FIWARE IDM source code repository is being hosted on GITHUB <https://github.com/ging/fiware-idm>.

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is the version 6.2, and it is being hosted on DOCKER Hub at the following link <https://hub.docker.com/r/waste4think/fiware-idm/>.

Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think project, FIWARE IDM has been deployed by using Docker technologies.

There are different ways to deploy the FIWARE IDM service. More information on this can be found in the official FIWARE IDM Installation & Administration Manual [11].

Two different ways can be used to deploy IDM by using Docker.

- Installation by using docker cli command;
- Installation by using docker-compose.

The docker-compose method has been used to deploy the IDM component in the Waste4Think context.

Docker cli method

```
docker run -d -name idm -p 8000:8000 -p 5000:5000 -t waste4think/fiware-idm
```

Check if all was successful by running:

```
docker ps
```

Docker compose method

In Table 43 the docker-compose.yml file used to deploy the FIWARE IDM version 6.2 instance in the Waste4Think Back-End environment is presented.

```
Version: "3"

services:
```

```
idm:

  image: waste4think/fiware-idm:latest

  hostname: keyrock

  container_name: keyrock

  ports:

    - "8000:8000"

    - "5000:5000"

networks:

  default:

    driver: bridge

    driver_opts:

      com.docker.network.driver.mtu: 1400
```

Table 43 – IDM docker compose file

Image: The IDM docker image used is the version 6.2 stored in the Waste4Think organization of the Docker HUB.

Ports: The port 8000 has been configured for the IDM component HORIZON (front-end), and the port 5000 has been configured for the IDM KEYSTONE component (back-end).

5.3.3. Manage FIWARE IDM Service

Start service: docker-compose up/-d command.

Stop service: docker-compose stop command or docker stop <idm-container>.

Service logs: docker logs <idm-container>

Access to the container of FIWARE IDM: docker exec -it < idm-container> bash

5.4. FIWARE AuthZForce

5.4.1. Service overall description

AUTHZFORCE is the reference implementation of the Authorization PDP Generic Enabler (formerly called Access Control GE). Indeed, as mandated by the GE specification, this implementation provides an API to get authorization decisions based on authorization policies, and authorization requests from PEPs. The API follows the REST architecture style and complies with XACML v3.0. XACML (extensible Access Control Markup Language) is an OASIS standard for authorization policy format and evaluation logic, as well as for the authorization decision request/response format. The PDP (Policy Decision Point) and the PEP (Policy Enforcement Point) terms are defined in the XACML standard. This GErI plays the role of a PDP.

5.4.2. Source code repository

The official FIWARE AuthZForce source code repository is being hosted on GITHUB <https://github.com/authzforce/fiware>.

The Docker image used in the Waste4Think project is the version 8.0.1, and it is being hosted on the Waste4Think project of the DOCKER Hub at the following link <https://hub.docker.com/r/waste4think/authzforce/>.

5.4.3. Installation/Configuration

In the Waste4Think project, FIWARE AuthZForce has been deployed by using Docker technologies.

There are different ways to deploy the FIWARE AuthZForce service. More information on that can be found in the official FIWARE AuthZForce Installation & Administration Manual [10].

Docker compose method

In Table 44, the docker-compose.yml file used to deploy the FIWARE AuthZForce component in the Waste4Think Back-End environment is presented.

```
version: "3"

services:
  authz:
    image: waste4think/authzforce:release-8.0.1
    ports:
      - "83:8080"

networks:
  default:
    driver: bridge
    driver_opts:
      com.docker.network.driver.mtu: 1400
```

Table 44 – AuthZForce docker compose file

Services and image used (hosted on waste4think docker-hub):

```
services: authz:
image: waste4think/authzforce:release-8.0.1
```

Port on witch docker container (AUTHZFORCE) will run

```
ports: "83:8080"
```

5.4.4. Manage FIWARE AuthZForce Service

Start service: docker-compose up/-d command.

Stop service: docker-compose stop command or docker stop <authz-container>.

Service logs: docker logs <authz-container>

Access to the container of FIWARE AuthZForce: docker exec -it < authz-container> bash

5.5. Applications, Users, Roles and Permission

In the Waste4Think IDM instance it was necessary to configure the following object:

- Application: Any securable FIWARE application consisting of a series of microservices
- User: Any signed up user able to identify themselves with an email and password. Users can be assigned rights individually or as a group
- Role: A role is a descriptive bucket for a set of permissions. A role can be assigned to either a single user or an organization. A signed-in user gains all the permissions from all of their own roles plus all of the roles associated with their organization
- Permission: An ability to do something on a resource within the system.

5.5.1. Applications

This section shows the back-end applications registered on IDM (see Figure 24).

Figure 24 - IDM Applications

The following Table 45 describes the application registered on IDM.

Application	Description
Waste4think	Waste management application, it contains a REST API interface whose purpose is to create and manage the entities of the pilot sites.

Table 45 - IDM Applications

5.5.2. Users and Roles

A set of users have been created and linked to the application in the FIWARE IDM service (see section 5.3). Each user represents an authorized user to access “Waste4Think” application registered on FIWARE IDM (see section 5.5.1). Moreover, for each user, a specific authorization role has been assigned.

The screenshot shows a web interface titled "Authorize users in your application". It features two main sections: "All users" and "Authorized Users". The "All users" section has a search filter box containing the text "Use the filter.". The "Authorized Users" section displays a list of users, each with a user icon, a name, a dropdown menu showing "1 roles", and a delete icon (x). The users listed are: dario, igor, enguser, seveso, zamudio, cascais, halandri, and W4TSortingAnalytics. At the bottom right, there are "Cancel" and "Save" buttons.

Figure 25 - IDM authorized user

The following Table 46 shows the list of authorized users and their roles associated with the IDM “waste4think” application.

User	Roles	Description
SEVESO (seveso)	PILOT (Pilot)	Seveso User
ZAMUDIO (zamudio)	PILOT (Pilot)	Zamudio User
CASCAIS (cascais)	PILOT (Pilot)	Cascais User
HALANDRI (halandri)	PILOT (Pilot)	Halandri
W4TSORTINGANALYTICS	PILOT	Pilot role given to external user in goal of

(W4TSortingAnalytics)	(Pilot)	developing internal application/game for waste4think project.
W4TOWNER (W4tOwner)	PROVIDER/OWNER (Provider/Owner)	Owner/creator of application, responsible for adding users and general administration specific to IDM.
ENGUSER (engUser)	ADMIN (Admin)	Administration role used to handle the IDM waste4think organization.

Table 46 - IDM Users and Roles

5.5.3. Permissions

The following Table 47 represents the list of the IDM permissions for each role.

Roles	Permission	Description
PILOT (pilot)	GET v2/entities	Permission to get all, single or entity based on type.
PILOT (pilot)	POST v2/op/update	Permission to create/update entities in batch operations.
ADMIN (Admin)	Version	Permission to get FIWARE Orion version
ADMIN (Admin)	GET v2/entities	Permission to get all, single or entity based on type.
ADMIN (Admin)	GET v2/subscriptions	Permission to get all created subscriptions
ADMIN (Admin)	GET v2/types	Permission to get all entities types or single one.
ADMIN (Admin)	GET v2/entities//attrs	Permission to retrieve entity attributes
ADMIN	POST v2/op/update	Permission to create/update entities in batch

(Admin)		operations.
ADMIN (Admin)	POST v2/subscriptions	Permission to create subscriptions
ADMIN (Admin)	POST v2/entities	Permission to create single entity
ADMIN (Admin)	POST v2/entities//attrs	Permission to update or append entity attributes
ADMIN (Admin)	PUT v2/entities	Permission to update entity attribute data
ADMIN (Admin)	PUT v2/entities//attrs//value	Permission to update entity attribute value
ADMIN (Admin)	PATCH v2/subscriptions	Permission to update entity subscription
ADMIN (Admin)	PATCH v2/entities//attrs	Permission to update existing entity attributes
ADMIN (Admin)	DELETE v2/subscriptions	Permission to remove subscription
ADMIN (Admin)	DELETE v2/entities	Permission to remove single entity
ADMIN (Admin)	DELETE v2/entities//attrs	Permission to remove entity attribute
PROVIDER/OWNER (Provider/Owner)	Manage the application	Permission to update, remove or edit application.
PROVIDER/OWNER (Provider/Owner)	Manage roles	Permission to create, remove roles
PROVIDER/OWNER (Provider/Owner)	Get and assign all public application roles	Permission to retrieve and assign roles.

PROVIDER/OWNER (Provider/Owner)	Manage Authorizations	Permission to authorize users in application and add them to it.
PROVIDER/OWNER (Provider/Owner)	Get and assign only public owned roles	Permission to assign public roles to user.
PROVIDER/OWNER (Provider/Owner)	Get and assign all internal application roles	Permission to assign internal roles in application ones who are for public users

Table 47 - IDM Roles and Permissions

6. Back-End interfaces to others Waste4Think modules

6.1. Front-End

All the Front-End applications in the Waste4Think ecosystem (Planning Tool, Zero Waste Events, Green Procurement, etc.) will communicate with the Back-End through the PyFiware connector.

6.1.1. PyFiware Connector

Service overall description

The PyFiware Connector is a Python library that provides a direct interface to use the NGSI v2 API commands to create, update and retrieve Waste4Think context entities in the Back-End. PyFiware makes the communication and the use of the FIWARE Context Broker OAuth protocol transparent to the application consumer.

Source code

The source code of the PyFiware Connector can be found on: <https://github.com/josubg/pyfiware>

Installation/Configuration

- To install PyFiware, run the following command:
 - `pip install pyfiware`
- To configure PyFiware, the user needs to define two sets of parameters, a) one for the specific instance of the Orion Context Broker (host, service, service path, and the OAuth connector, and b) the parameters relevant to the OAuth specification (id, secret, user and password).

Table 48 shows an example of the configuration of the PyFiware Connector.

```

from pyfiware import OrionConnector
from pyfiware.oauth import OAuthManager

oauth= OAuthManager(
    oauth_server_url='http://backend.waste4think.eu:8000/oauth2',
    client_id="3bb5a3ee06854161a05bfdcdeab7c1cf",
    client_secret="82e2f867b9db441ea0dd3659e05cbdcc",
    user="josu.bermudez@deusto.es",
    password="82e2f867b9db441ea0dd3659e05cbdcc"
)

oc = OrionConnector(
    host="http://backend.waste4think.eu/",
    service="waste4think",
    service_path="/#",
    oauth_connector=oauth
)

oc.search("SortingType")[3]['color']['value']

```

Table 48 – Example configuration of the PyFiware connector

6.2. Sensors

Waste4Think pilots can provide different information as sensors data (lock system, weighting system, GPS system) and/or data coming from legacy system deployed in the pilots (MAWIS, Ge.R.A., ILink) to the Back-End.

As described in section 9 of the D2.1 [3], Waste4Think pilots can opt for different methods to upload their data (sensors, legacy system, etc.) to the back-end (see Figure 26 - Uploading systems). These systems provide pilots different approaches to handle uploading data, with the aim to cover several scenarios such as near real-time process, batch process and upload process that require user interaction.

Figure 26 - Uploading systems

6.2.1. NGSICConnectorAPI

Service overall description

The NGSICConnectorAPI is a RESTful web service that allows authorised Waste4Think users to create, update and retrieve Waste4Think context entities in the Back-End platform.

NGSICConnectorAPI has been developed by using NodeJS[20] technologies, specific Express JS framework[22].

NGSICConnectorAPI uses NGSI V2 API provided by FIWARE Orion. It provides functionalities to upload a large amount of data stored in CSV o JSON files, by automating the process, checking data with predefined rules and summarising the operation results.

NGSICConnectorAPI endpoint

The NGSICConnectorAPI is running at the following link:

<http://backend.waste4think.eu/connector>.

Source code

The source code of the NGSICConnectorAPI is being hosted on GITLAB at the following link:

<http://dev.waste4think.eu/waste4think/NgsiConnector>.

The docker image used in the Waste4Think project is being hosted on the Waste4Think project of the DOCKER Hub and is available at the following link:

<https://hub.docker.com/r/waste4think/ngsi-connector/>.

Installation/Configuration

NGSICConnectorAPI has been installed using docker-compose.

In the Table 49 the docker-compose file used to configure and deploy the NGSICConnectorAPI to Waste4Think back-end is presented.

```
version: "3"

services:

  connector:

    image: waste4think/ngsi-connector:3.0.0

    volumes:

      - /data/docker_connector/conf/config.js:/opt/ocbconnector/config.js

    ports:

      - "3000:3000"

networks:

  default:

    driver: bridge

    driver_opts:
```

```
com.docker.network.driver.mtu: 1400
```

Table 49 – NGSConnectorAPI docker compose file

```
connector:
```

```
image: waste4think/ngsi-connector
```

Services and image used (hosted on Waste4Think docker-hub organization).

```
ports: "3000:3000"
```

Port of the NGSConnectorAPI service.

```
/data/docker_connector/conf/config.js:/opt/ocbconnector/config.js
```

Volume that map the NGSConnectorAPI configuration file.

Configuration file

In the Table 50 the configuration file used by the NGSConnectorAPI service is presented.

```
const config = {};
config.orion_url = 'http://192.168.229.62:82/';
config.api_port = '3000';
config.ext = ['.csv'];
config.https = true;
config.returnEntities = 20;
module.exports = config;
```

Table 50 - NGSConnectorAPI config file

```
config.orion_url:
```

FIWARE Orion URL. In the Waste4Think context FIWARE ORION Context Broker is protected by PEP-PROXY and then the value 'http://192.168.229.62:82/' represents the URL of PEP Proxy service.

```
config.api_port:
```

NGSConnectorAPI port.

```
config.ext:
```

Supported file extensions to upload/update context information in the FIWARE Orion Context Broker. At the time of writing of this deliverable, the NGISConnectorAPI supports csv and json extensions.

```
config.https:
```

Running the NGISConnectorAPI in HTTPS mode. Values admitted “true” and “false”.

```
config.returnEntities:
```

Number of entities to get from the Context Broker. This is a parameter of the FIWARE ORION Context Broker which return by default 20 entities when using GET all entities operations. With this option, we can increase the number up to 1000.

NGISConnectorAPI supporting tool

NGISConnectorAPI has been documented using a powerful open source framework Swagger [15] that helps to design, build, document and consume RESTful API. REST API documentation is available within the deployed app through Swagger annotation at the following link:

<http://backend.waste4think.eu:81/>.

The Swagger documentation can be split into three main sections:

- General description of the project that includes developers, https/http license etc. (see Figure 27)

Figure 27 - APIs swagger description

- List of APIs provided by the NGSConnectorAPI service (see Figure 28).

Entities	
GET	/entities List of entities
POST	/entities Create entities from user file
GET	/entities/{entityId} Entity by ID
GET	/entities/type/{typeId} List of Entities by type
POST	/entities/update Update entities from user file
GET	/rules List of all available rules
GET	/rules{ruleId} Return single rule

Figure 28 - swagger API list

- Information on data models defined in the Waste4Think project (see Figure 29).

Models	
DepositPointType	>
DepositionPoint	>
ResourceCategory	>
SortingType	>
Resource	>
DepositPointsIsle	>
Transaction	> {...}
Vehicle	> {...}
VehicleType	>

Figure 29 - swagger data model info

[Annex C](#) contains an exploded view of each API call definition which includes i) implementation notes, ii) query parameters and iii) response data model.

6.2.2. NGSConnectorWEB

Service overall description

The NGSConnectorWEB is a web application which exposes the NGSConnectorAPI functionalities and provides Waste4Think users with a graphical interface for work on them. On top of functionalities provided by NGSConnectorAPI, NGSConnectorWEB is also

responsible for access token management, specifically for automating the process of token retrieval.

NGSICConnectorWEB is developed with NodeJS [17] and ExpressJS [18] technologies, as they offer great speed, a huge set of functionalities and very stable environment.

NGSICConnectorWEB endpoint

NGSICConnectorWEB is running at the following link:

<http://backend.waste4think.eu:3001>

Source code

The source code of the NGSICConnectorWEB is being hosted on the following link:

<http://dev.waste4think.eu/waste4think/NgsiConnectorWeb>

The Docker image is being hosted on the Waste4Think project of the Docker Hub on the following link:

<https://hub.docker.com/r/waste4think/ngsi-connector-web/>

Installation/Configuration

NGSICConnectorWEB has been deployed using docker-compose.

In Table 51, the docker-compose file used to configure and deploy the NGSICConnectorWEB to Waste4Think back-end is presented.

```
version: "3"

services:
  connector:
    image: waste4think/ngsi-connector-web:2.0.1
    volumes:
      -
        /data/docker_connector_web/conf/config.js:/opt/NgsiConnectorWeb/config.js
    ports:
      - "3001:3001"
  networks:
    default:
      driver: bridge
```

```
driver_opts:
    com.docker.network.driver.mtu: 1400
```

Table 51 – NGSICConnectorWEB docker-compose file

```
connector:
```

```
image: waste4think/ngsi-connector-web:2.0.1
```

Services and image used (hosted on Waste4Think docker-hub organization)

```
ports: "3001:3001"
```

Port on which the NGSICConnectorWEB docker container is running.

```
/data/docker_connector_web/conf/config.js:/opt/NgsiConnectorWeb/config.js
```

Volume that map the NGSICConnectorWEB configuration file on an external folder.

Configuration file

Configuration file used by the NGSICConnectorWEB service is presented.

```
"url": "https://192.168.229.62:3000/v1",
"port": 3001,
"clientID": "3bb5a3ee06854161a05bfdcdeab7c1cf",
"clientSecret": "82e2f867b9db441ea0dd3659e05cbdcc"
```

Table 52 – NGSICConnectorWEB configuration file.

```
url:
```

NGSICConnectorAPI URL, used by NGSICConnectorWEB for API calls.

```
port:
```

NGSICConnectorWEB port.

```
clientID:
```

```
clientSecret:
```

ClientID and ClientSecret of the “Waste4think” application defined in the FIWARE IDM instance (see section 5.3 of this deliverable) to get access token in NGSICConnectorWEB interface.

NGSConnectorWEB interface

The NGSConnectorWEB interface is structured in different web pages which provide different functionality to the Waste4Think users.

Login page

The NGSConnectorWEB login page is used to authenticate Waste4Think users. (see Figure 30).

Figure 30 - NGSConnectorWEB Login page

Home page

It provides quick access feature to most used functionalities as well as navigation menu to all pages available (see Figure 31).

Figure 31 - NGSConnectorWEB Home page

Entities page

Entities page provides the functionality to get all entities specifying Fiware-Service and Fiware-ServicePath (see Figure 32).

NGSIConnectorWEB

Please provide Fiware-Service and Fiware-Service-Path and procede to list entities from it.

Depending on Fiware-Service and Fiware-Service-Path different results will be presented

Fiware-Service

Enter Fiware-Service...

Fiware-Service-Path

/deusto/w4t/zamudio/real

Access-Token

Enter Access-Token...

List Entities Get Access Token

Figure 32 - NGSIConnectorWEB Entities page

Details page

Details page provides the functionality to get a single entity specifying Fiware-Service and Fiware-ServicePath (see Figure 33).

NGSIConnectorWEB

Please provide Fiware-Service and Fiware-Service-Path and procede to list details of single entity from it.

Depending on Fiware-Service and Fiware-Service-Path different results will be presented

Fiware-Service

Enter Fiware-Service a file

Fiware-Service-Path

/deusto/w4t/zamudio/real

Access-Token

Enter Access-Token...

Entity-ID

Enter Entity ID

Show Entity Get Access Token

Figure 33 - NGSIConnectorWEB Details page

Type page

Type page provides the functionality to get entities specifying Entity Type, Fiware-Service and Fiware-ServicePath (see Figure 34).

NGSISConnectorWEB

Please provide Fiware-Service and Fiware-Service-Path and procede to list entities of given type.

Depending on Fiware-Service and Fiware-Service-Path different results will be presented

Fiware-Service

Fiware-Service-Path

Access-Token

Entity-Type

Figure 34 - NGSISConnectorWEB Type page

Create page

Create page provides the functionality to create entities from user-supplied file specifying Fiware-Service and Fiware-ServicePath (see Figure 35).

NGSISConnectorWEB

Please chose .csv file and procede to update entities from it.

Entity type in file must be equal to: DepositPoint, DepositPointType, Waste, SortingType, Vehicle, VehicleType, Transaction and other entities

Fiware-Service

Fiware-Service-Path

Access-Token

File for upload
 No file chosen

Figure 35 - NGSISConnectorWEB Create page

Update page

Update page provides the functionality to update entities from user-supplied file specifying Fiware-Service and Fiware-ServicePath (see Figure 36).

NGSICconnectorWEB

Please chose .csv file and procede to update entities from it.

Entity type in file must be equal to: DepositPoint, DepositPointType, Waste, SortingType, Vehicle, VehicleType, Transaction and other entities

Fiware-Service

Fiware-Service-Path

Access-Token

File for upload
 No file chosen

Figure 36 - NGSICconnectorWEB Update page

Rules page

Rules page provides the functionality to show information the available rules defined in the Waste4Think data model (see Figure 37).

NGSICconnectorWEB

Please enter rule name to get more detail information.

Rule Name

Figure 37 - NGSICconnectorWEB Rules page

Access token

NGSICconnectorWEB access token form (see Figure 38) provides a function to retrieve the access token using a FIWARE IDM credential (see section 5.3 of this deliverable).

Email

Password

Figure 38 - NGSICconnectorWEB Access token form

6.2.3. NGS API

FIWARE-NGSI v2 APIs[24] is a RESTful API provided by FIWARE Orion Context Broker to manage the entire lifecycle of context information, including updates, queries, registrations, and subscriptions.

Details about FIWARE-NGSI v2 APIs has been already described in the deliverable 2.1 [3].

6.3. Treatment Plants

This procedure will update the status of the operation and the amount of waste processed in each of the treatment plants featured in the Waste4Think project:

- Biomass production from food/kitchen waste monitorization (R19) Section 7.3 D3.1 [25];
- Biofuel and Compost production from disposable nappies (R20) Section 8 of D3.3[26];

In the case of the status of the operation, the CSV output files produced by the SCADA systems of the treatment plants will be parsed by the NGSConnectorAPI and the information will reach the different attributes of the data model. On the other hand, for the waste processed, handmade CSV files will be uploaded and parsed by the NGSConnectorAPI. Both procedures will be performed after every batch of operation of the treatment plant. Further information about the specifications of the SCADA systems can be found in Deliverable D3.1, Section 7.3 for R19, and Deliverable D3.3, Section 8 for R20.

Table 53 and Table 54 shows an example of the CSV file detailing the status of the treatment operation for R19 and R20. Table 55 and Table 56 show an example of the CSV file detailing the amount of waste processed for R19 and R20.

Time	pH Methanogenic Reactor	temp Methanogenic Reactor	pH Acidogenic Reactor	temp Acidogenic Reactor
02/10/2015 10:52	Bad	Bad	Bad	Bad
02/10/2015 10:55	Bad	Bad	Bad	Bad
02/10/2015 11:59	9.05696	44.4416	5.80772	15.3927
02/10/2015 12:00	9.05696	44.4387	5.80732	15.3939
02/10/2015 16:00	9.08748	42.6506	5.80543	15.3902
02/10/2015 20:00	9.11096	40.8522	5.80579	15.2838

Table 53 - Example CSV file with the information of the status in R20

Day	Temperature (°C) (sensor)	Moisture Content (%) (manually)	pH (manually)	Electrical conductivity (EC) [mS/cm] (manually)	Total solids (TS) [g]	TS [%]	Volatile solids (VS) [g]	TOC [%]	N (TKN) [%]	N (mg/g)
1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

2	52.1			-						
3	57.7	39.12	6.3	-				50.560	2.222	22.217
4	55.4	35.99	-	-						
5	61.6	35.22	-	-				49.393	2.286	22.861
6	61.4	35.19	6.27	2.08						
7	62	39.6	6.6	2.2	1.74	62.81	1.4021	47.185	2.437	24.366
8	60	38.58	6.91	2.28	1.55	66.41	1.3683			
9	59.2	39.55	6.82	2.28	2.01	67.56	1.6906	48.762	2.439	24.388
10	49.6	35.64	6.82	2.28	-	-	-			
11	55.9	45.03	-	-	-	-	-		2.657	26.570
12	61.6	-	-	-	-	-	-			
13	57.2	41.24	6.93	2.4	1.32	60.10	1.0981			
14	62	42.95	-	-	-	-	-			
15	56.8	45.52	7.22	2.46	1.67	54.46	1.3959			
16	46.7	44.57	7.24	2.4	2.05	55.91	1.7154			
17	51.6	41.96	7.41	2.48	2.30	63.86	1.8289			

Table 54 - Example CSV file with the information of the status in R19

Week	Fruits and vegetables [kg]	Edible starchy products [kg]	Pilot Feed		Pilot Output					
			Edible animal products/byproducts [kg]	Used, disposable infant nappies [#]	Used, disposable adult nappies [#]	SAP [Kg]	Plastics [Kg]	Compost [Kg]	Biogas STP [L]	Thermal energy equivalent [MJ]
1	100.1	200.3	450.6	320	105	75.9	70.2	65.3	20.8	58.8
2	150.2	275.2	500.9	300	120	80.7	52.1	46.5	27.3	60.2
3	200.5	450.2	415.9	275	136	90.4	32.6	58.8	25.9	35.2

Table 55 - Example CSV file with the information of processed materials in R20

Date	3/1/18	4/1/18	5/1/18	8/1/18	9/1/18	10/1/18	11/1/18	12/1/18	15/1/18	16/1/18
Morning batch										
weight of HFW (Kg)	111	115	111	115	115	116	115	116	116	135
weight of FORBI (Kg)	22.8	17.7	27	34	31.7	26	26.4	17	25.2	25.9
electricity counter index (start of every cycle) (kW)	26650	26756	26843	26934	27117		27389	27560	27740	27925
electricity counter index (end of every cycle) (kW)	26756	26843	26934	27026	27197	27389	27475	27641	27827	28036
energy consumption (kW)	106	87	91	92	80	27389	86	81	87	111
Afternoon batch										
weight of HFW (Kg)				115	115		116	115	130	130
weight of FORBI (Kg)				22.4	26.7		19	24.3	30.8	27.1

electricity counter index (start of every cycle) (kW)	27026	27197	27475	27641	27827	28036
electricity counter index (end of every cycle) (kW)	27117		27560	27740	27925	28132
energy consumption (kW)	91		85	99	98	96

Table 56 - Example CSV file with the information of processed materials in R19

6.4. Serious Games & APPs

Both the Serious Games and the APPs will connect directly to the FIWARE ORION Context Broker using the FIWARE-NGSI version 2 API [24] interfaces directly or indirectly using the PyFiware library. In both cases, these modules will update the relevant UserMetrics entities defined in the Waste4Think data model after each use of the platform.

Examples of the data sent from the Serious Games and the APPs to the Context Broker are shown in Table 57, Table 58 and Table 59.

```
{
  "id": "5bed2fcc-ef25-45f1-92fc-3d7992498991",
  "type": "CitizenAppUserMetrics",
  "search": {
    "type": "Text",
    "value": "paper containers",
    "metadata": {}
  }
}
```

Table 57 - Example JSON with the information of a user session in the Citizen App

```
{
  "id": "de46fccc-c951-11e8-a8d5-f2801f1b9fd1",
  "type": "FoodAppUserTransaction",
  "donor": {
    "type": "Text",
    "value": "5bed2fcc-ef25-45f1-92fc-3d7992498991",
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "donee": {
    "type": "Text",
    "value": "6799a08c-c950-11e8-a8d5-f2801f1b9fd1",
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "product": {
    "type": "Text",
    "value": "Cooked pasta",
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "weight": {
    "type": "Number",
    "value": "20",
    "metadata": {
      "unit": "kg",
    }
  },
  "allergens": {
    "type": "Text",
    "value": "cheese, nuts"
  },
}
```

}

Table 58 - Example JSON with the information of a user transaction in the Food App

```

{
  "id": "5bed2fcc-ef25-45f1-92fc-3d7992498991",
  "type": "SortingGameUserMetrics",
  "age": {
    "type": "Number",
    "value": 27,
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "gender": {
    "type": "Text",
    "value": "MALE",
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "municipalityName": {
    "type": "Text",
    "value": "Zamudio",
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "countryName": {
    "type": "Text",
    "value": "Spain",
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "maxLevel": { //The furthest level the user has reached
    "type": "Number",
    "value": 2,
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "totalPlayedLevels": { //The total number of level play-throughs,
including replayed levels
    "type": "Number",
    "value": 2,
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "totalPoints": {
    "type": "Number",
    "value": 150,
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "totalItems_All": {
    "type": "Number",
    "value": 20,
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "totalIncorrectItems_All": {
    "type": "Number",
    "value": 4,
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "totalItems_TypeID_1053": { // Total number of items from the sorting
type with ID 1053 that have been presented to the user
    "type": "Number",
    "value": 10,
    "metadata": {}
  },
  "totalIncorrectItems_TypeID_1053": { // Total number of errors in the
sorting type with ID 1053 that the user has made
    "type": "Number",
    "value": 2,
    "metadata": {}
  }
}

```

```

    },
    "totalItems_TypeID_1054": {
      "type": "Number",
      "value": 5,
      "metadata": {}
    },
    "totalIncorrectItems_TypeID_1054": {
      "type": "Number",
      "value": 1,
      "metadata": {}
    },
    "totalItems_TypeID_1055": {
      "type": "Number",
      "value": 5,
      "metadata": {}
    },
    "totalIncorrectItems_TypeID_1055": {
      "type": "Number",
      "value": 1,
      "metadata": {}
    }
  }
}

```

Table 59 - Example JSON with the information of a user session in the Serious Games

6.5. Learning Materials

Learning materials will retrieve information using several online surveys. The results of these surveys will be processed regularly and introduced in the platform as a UserMetric entity. To this end, a person will manually download the results of the surveys using the CSV export tool and will use the NGSIConectorAPI to upload the information to the platform. An example of this CSV with information of the Learning Materials is shown in the Table 60.

LM_ID	Age Range	Students involved	Effectiveness	Relevance	Objective	Contents	Motivate	Recipients	Evaluation	...	Data
1	5-7	12	4	4	2	3	4	5	3	...	4
2	5-7	12	3	5	4	3	5	4	3	...	4
3	5-7	12	4	5	4	3	4	5	4	...	5
4	5-7	12	3	4	5	3	5	6	5	...	4
6	5-7	12	5	5	3	3	3	4	5	...	4
...

Table 60 - Example CSV with the information of the Learning Materials

7. References

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- [10] FIWARE AuthZForce PDP - <https://authzforce-ce-fiware.readthedocs.io/en/latest/InstallationAndAdministrationGuide.html>
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- [25] Deliverable 3.1 “*Technical Documentation of R19: Biomass Production from food/kitchen Waste*”
- [26] Deliverable 3.3 “*Technical Documentation of R20: Biofuels and Compost Production From Disposable Napies*”

Annex A - Docker manual

Docker is an open platform for developing, shipping, and running applications. Docker enables you to separate your applications from your infrastructure, so you can deliver software quickly. With Docker, you can manage your infrastructure in the same ways you manage your applications. By taking advantage of Docker's methodologies for shipping, testing, and deploying code quickly, you can significantly reduce the delay between writing code.

Usage of Docker

Docker streamlines the development lifecycle by allowing developers to work in standardized environments using local containers which provide your application and services. Containers are great for continuous integration and continuous delivery (CI/CD) workflows.

Consider the following example scenario:

- Developers write code locally and share their work with their colleagues using Docker containers.
- Use Docker to push their applications into a test environment and execute automated and manual tests.
- When developers find bugs, they can fix them in a development environment and redeploy them to the test environment for testing and validation.
- When testing is complete, getting the fix to the customer is as simple as pushing the updated image to the production environment.

Responsive deployment and scaling

Docker's container-based platform allows for highly portable workloads. Docker containers can run on a developer's local laptop, on physical or virtual machines in a data center, on cloud providers, or in a mixture of environments.

Docker's portability and lightweight nature also make it easy to dynamically manage workloads, scaling up or tearing down applications and services as business needs dictate, in near real time.

Running more workloads on the same hardware

Docker is lightweight and fast. It provides a viable, cost-effective alternative to hypervisor-based virtual machines, so you can use more of your compute capacity to achieve your business goals. Docker is perfect for high-density environments and for small and medium deployments where you need to do more with fewer resources.

Installation of Docker

The first step determines whether any updates are available for our installed packages.

```
➤ sudo yum check-update
```

Then running following command will add the official Docker repository, download the latest version of Docker, and install it:

```
➤ sudo curl -fsSl https://get.docker.com/ | sh
```

After installation is complete then we start the Docker daemon:

```
➤ sudo systemctl start docker
```

Verifying that docker is running:

```
➤ sudo systemctl status docker
```

The output of this command should be similar to the following, showing that service is active and running.

Output

```
● docker.service - Docker Application Container Engine
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/docker.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Sun 2016-05-01 06:53:52 CDT; 1 weeks 3 days ago
     Docs: https://docs.docker.com
   Main PID: 749 (docker)
```

Lastly, make sure it starts at every server reboot:

```
➤ sudo systemctl enable docker
```

Installing Docker now give not just the Docker service (daemon) but also the *docker* command line utility, or the Docker client.

Executing Docker Command without sudo (Optional)

By default, running the `docker` command requires root privileges – that is, you have to prefix the command with `sudo`. It can also be run by a user in `docker` group, which is automatically created during the installation of Docker. If you attempt to run the `docker` command without a prefix it with `sudo` or without being in the `docker` group, you will get an output like this:

Output

```
docker: Cannot connect to the Docker daemon. Is the docker daemon running on this host?.
See 'docker run --help'.
```

To avoid typing `sudo` to run docker command, add username to docker group:

```
➤ sudo usermod -aG docker $(username)
```

Logout of Virtual Machine for settings to work. If there is a need of adding some other user that is not logged in use following command.

```
➤ sudo usermod -aG docker username
```

Docker commands

With Docker installed and working, time to become familiar with the command line utility. Using `docker` consist of passing it a chain of option and subcommands followed by arguments. The syntax takes this form:

```
➤ docker [ option] [ command] [ arguments]
```

To see all available subcommands, type:

```
➤ docker
```

Complete list of all commands will be displayed

```
Output

attach      Attach to a running container
build       Build an image from a Dockerfile
commit      Create a new image from a container's changes
cp          Copy files/folders between a container and the local filesystem
create      Create a new container
diff        Inspect changes on a container's filesystem
events      Get real time events from the server
exec        Run a command in a running container
export      Export a container's filesystem as a tar archive
history     Show the history of an image
images      List images
import      Import the contents from a tarball to create a filesystem image
info        Display system-wide information
inspect     Return low-level information on a container or image
kill        Kill a running container
load        Load an image from a tar archive or STDIN
login       Log in to a Docker registry
logout      Log out from a Docker registry
logs        Fetch the logs of a container
network     Manage Docker networks
pause       Pause all processes within a container
port        List port mappings or a specific mapping for the CONTAINER
ps          List containers
pull        Pull an image or a repository from a registry
push        Push an image or a repository to a registry
rename      Rename a container
restart     Restart a container
rm          Remove one or more containers
rmi         Remove one or more images
run         Run a command in a new container
save        Save one or more images to a tar archive
search      Search the Docker Hub for images
start       Start one or more stopped containers
stats       Display a live stream of container(s) resource usage statistics
stop        Stop a running container
tag         Tag an image into a repository
top         Display the running processes of a container
unpause     Unpause all processes within a container
update      Update configuration of one or more containers
version     Show the Docker version information
volume     Manage Docker volumes
wait        Block until a container stops, then print its exit code
```

To view more info about a specific command, type:

```
➤ docker docker-subcommand -help
```

To see system-wide information, type:

```
➤ docker info
```

Docker images

Docker containers are run from Docker images. By default, it pulls these images from Docker Hub, a Docker registry managed by Docker, the company behind the Docker project. Anybody can build and host their Docker images on Docker Hub, so most applications and Linux distribution need to run Docker container have images that are hosted on Docker Hub.

To check whether user can access and download images from Docker Hub, type:

```
➤ docker run hello-world
```

The output, which should include the following, should indicate that Docker is working correctly:

```
Output
Hello from Docker.
This message shows that your installation appears to be working correctly.
...
```

There is an option to search for images on Docker Hub by using the docker command with the search subcommand. For example, to search for the waste4think image, type:

```
➤ docker search waste4think
```

This will crawl Docker Hub and return a listing of all images whose name match the search string.

In the **OFFICIAL** column, **OK** indicates an image built and supported by the company behind the project.

Lifecycle commands from pulling image to running it:

```
➤ docker pull [image_name]
```

```
➤ docker run image
```

To see images downloaded:

```
docker images
```

The output should look like the following (it is different depending images that are being downloaded):

```
[secondary_label Output]
REPOSITORY          TAG                 IMAGE ID            CREATED             SIZE
centos               latest              778a53015523       5 weeks ago        196.7 MB
hello-world         latest              94df4f0ce8a4       2 weeks ago        967 B
```

Listing and showing Docker containers

After using Docker for a while, there will be many active(running) and inactive containers on the machine.

To see active ones:

```
➤ docker ps
```

To see all containers active and inactive, pass the **-a** switch:

```
➤ docker ps -a
```

To see the latest container that was created, pass the `-l` switch:

```
> docker ps -l
```

To stop running or active container type:

```
> docker stop container name/id can be obtain using docker ps command
```

To remove container/image

```
> docker rm/rmi containerId/imageId
```

Docker-Compose Service

Compose is a tool for defining and running multi-container Docker applications. Compose use a YAML file to configure application services. Then, with a single command, you create and start all the services from your configuration.

Compose works in all environments: production, staging, development, testing, as well as CI workflows.

To use Compose it require three-step process:

- Define apps environment with `Dockerfile` so it can be reproduced anywhere.
- Define the services that make up the app in `docker-compose.yml` so they can be run together in an isolated environment.
- Run `docker-compose up` and Compose starts and run the entire app

Example of `docker-compose.yml` looks like this:

```
version: '3'
services:
  web:
    build: .
    ports:
      - "5000:5000"
    volumes:
      - ./code
      - logvolume01:/var/log
    links:
      - redis
  redis:
    image: redis
volumes:
  logvolume01: {}
```

Key compose parts:

version: '3'

- There are 3 versions of docker-compose 1, 2, and 3. Version represents what set of features or limitations are available to the user. There is a difference between versions.

services

- Different parts of the application are called services, they are nothing but containers that will be created with specific commands being added to them.

ports

- Representing ports on which service will be run.

volumes

- Main use of volumes is persisting data on the user machine, once docker container is removed it loses all its saved data. Volumes allow us to map location on the local drive to containers drive, or in some case to pass `config` file if some service requires one.

Annex B – FIWARE Orion subscriptions

Table 61 shows an example of Orion subscriptions which notify entities to Historical Module based on InfluxDB.

```
[{
  "id": "5b51b05464493217476ed4ca",
  "description": "A subscription to get info about DepositPoint
entity",
  "expires": "2040-01-01T14:00:00.00Z",
  "status": "active",
  "subject": {
    "entities": [{
      "idPattern": ".*",
      "type": "DepositPoint"
    }],
    "condition": {
      "attrs": []
    }
  },
  "notification": {
    "timesSent": 1,
    "lastNotification": "2018-07-20T09:50:12.00Z",
    "attrs": [],
    "attrsFormat": "normalized",
    "http": {
      "url":
"http://history.deusto.io/api/fiware/scenario/deusto:w4t:zamudio:real/entit
ies"
    },
    "lastSuccess": "2018-07-20T09:50:12.00Z"
  },
  "throttling": 5
},
{
```

```

    "id": "5b51b06564493217476ed4cb",

    "description": "A subscription to get info about DepositPointType
entity",

    "expires": "2040-01-01T14:00:00.00Z",

    "status": "active",

    "subject": {

        "entities": [{

            "idPattern": ".*",

            "type": "DepositPointType"

        }],

        "condition": {

            "attrs": []

        }

    },

    "notification": {

        "timesSent": 1,

        "lastNotification": "2018-07-20T09:50:29.00Z",

        "attrs": [],

        "attrsFormat": "normalized",

        "http": {

            "url":

"http://history.deusto.io/api/fiware/scenario/deusto:w4t:zamudio:real/entit
ies"

        },

        "lastSuccess": "2018-07-20T09:50:30.00Z"

    },

    "throttling": 5

},

{

    "id": "5b51b07764493217476ed4cc",

    "description": "A subscription to get info about Vehicle entity",

    "expires": "2040-01-01T14:00:00.00Z",

    "status": "active",

```

```

"subject": {
  "entities": [{
    "idPattern": ".*",
    "type": "Vehicle"
  }],
  "condition": {
    "attrs": []
  }
},
"notification": {
  "timesSent": 1,
  "lastNotification": "2018-07-20T09:50:47.00Z",
  "attrs": [],
  "attrsFormat": "normalized",
  "http": {
    "url":
"http://history.deusto.io/api/fiware/scenario/deusto:w4t:zamudio:real/entities"
  },
  "lastSuccess": "2018-07-20T09:50:47.00Z"
},
"throttling": 5
},
{
  "id": "5b51b08f64493217476ed4cd",
  "description": "A subscription to get info about VehicleType entity",
  "expires": "2040-01-01T14:00:00.00Z",
  "status": "active",
  "subject": {
    "entities": [{
      "idPattern": ".*",
      "type": "VehicleType"
    }],

```

```

        "condition": {
            "attrs": []
        }
    },
    "notification": {
        "timesSent": 1,
        "lastNotification": "2018-07-20T09:51:11.00Z",
        "attrs": [],
        "attrsFormat": "normalized",
        "http": {
            "url":
"http://history.deusto.io/api/fiware/scenario/deusto:w4t:zamudio:real/entities"
        },
        "lastSuccess": "2018-07-20T09:51:11.00Z"
    },
    "throttling": 5
},
{
    "id": "5b51bed164493217476ed4ce",
    "description": "A subscription to get info about SortingType entity",
    "expires": "2040-01-01T14:00:00.00Z",
    "status": "active",
    "subject": {
        "entities": [{
            "idPattern": ".*",
            "type": "SortingType"
        }],
        "condition": {
            "attrs": []
        }
    },
    "notification": {

```

```

    "timesSent": 1,
    "lastNotification": "2018-07-20T10:52:01.00Z",
    "attrs": [],
    "attrsFormat": "normalized",
    "http": {
        "url":
"http://history.deusto.io/api/fiware/scenario/deusto:w4t:zamudio:real/entities"
    }
},
    "throttling": 5
}}

```

Table 61 - Example FIWARE ORION subscriptions to InfluxDB

Table 61 shows an example of Orion subscription which notifies entities to CEP system.

```

curl -v http://backend.waste4think.eu/v2/subscriptions -s -S --header 'Content-Type:
application/json' \
  -d @- <<EOF
{
  "description": "A subscription to get information about
DepositPointIsles",
  "subject": {
    "entities": [
      {
        "id": "#",
        "type": "DepositPointIsle"
      }
    ],
    "condition": {
      "attrs": [
"location", "address", "name", "description", "refDepositPoint",
"areaServed", "dateModified", "dateCreated"
]
    }
  },
  "notification": {
    "http": {
      "url": "http://sandwich.geoworldsim.com/api/app/:SANDWICH_ID/execute"
    },
    "attrs": [
      "location", "address", "name", "description", "refDepositPoint",
"areaServed", "dateModified", "dateCreated"
    ]
  }
}

```

```

    },
    "throttling": 5
  }
}
EOF

```

Table 62 - Example FIWARE ORION subscription to CEP

Table 63 shows an example of Orion subscriptions which notify entities to FIWARE Cygnus connector.

```

{
  "description": "A subscription to get info about DepositPointIsle
entity",
  "subject": {
    "entities": [
      {
        "idPattern": ".*",
        "type": "DepositPointIsle"
      }
    ],
    "condition": {
      "attrs": [

      ]
    }
  },
  "notification": {
    "http": {
      "url": "http://192.168.229.62:5050/notify"
    },
    "attrsFormat": "legacy",
    "attrs": [

    ]
  },
  "expires": "2040-01-01T14:00:00.00Z",

```

```
"throttling": 5
}

{
  "description": "A subscription to get info about DepositPoint entity",
  "subject": {
    "entities": [
      {
        "idPattern": ".*",
        "type": "DepositPoint"
      }
    ],
    "condition": {
      "attrs": [

      ]
    }
  },
  "notification": {
    "http": {
      "url": "http://192.168.229.62:5050/notify"
    },
    "attrsFormat": "legacy",
    "attrs": [

    ]
  },
  "expires": "2040-01-01T14:00:00.00Z",
  "throttling": 5
}

{
  "description": "A subscription to get info about DepositPointType
```

```
entity",
  "subject": {
    "entities": [
      {
        "idPattern": ".*",
        "type": "DepositPointType"
      }
    ],
    "condition": {
      "attrs": [
        ]
      }
    },
    "notification": {
      "http": {
        "url": "http://192.168.229.62:5050/notify"
      },
      "attrsFormat": "legacy",
      "attrs": [
        ]
    },
    "expires": "2040-01-01T14:00:00.00Z",
    "throttling": 5
  }
}
```

Table 63 - Example FIWARE ORION subscriptions to FIWARE Cygnus

Annex C – NGSConnectorAPI service APIs

GET /entities

Get list of entities specifying Service and ServicePath (see Figure 39).

Entities Entities

GET /entities List of entities

Retrieves a list of entities by specifying Service and ServicePath

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
Fiware-Service * required string (header)	Service of entities
Fiware-ServicePath * required string (header)	Service Path of entities
X-Auth-Token * required string (header)	Access Token For Orion

Responses Response content type: application/json

Code	Description
200	Object that contain result of requested operation success or fail will be presented
401	The request has not been applied because it lacks valid authentication credentials for the target resource.
503	There are no server resources to fulfill the client request.

Example Value | Model

```
[
  {
    "id": "string",
    "type": "string",
    "name": "string",
    "description": "string",
    "width": 0,
    "height": 0,
    "depth": 0,
    "weight": 0,
    "cargoVolume": 0,
    "maximumLoad": 0,
    "recommendedLoad": 0,
    "category": [
      "string"
    ],
    "insertHolesNumber": 0,
    "insertHolesWidth": 0,
    "loadType": "string",
    "madeOf": "string",
    "madeOfCode": "string",
    "brandName": "string",
    "modelName": "string",
    "manufacturerName": "string",
    "colors": [
      "string"
    ]
  }
]
```

Figure 39 - GET /entities

POST /entities

Upload entities in the back-end from user supplied file (csv, json) (see Figure 40).

POST /entities Create entities from user file

Create entities from user supplied file (csv, json, text)

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
Fiware-Service * required string (header)	Service of entities
Fiware-ServicePath * required string (header)	Service Path of entities
X-Auth-Token * required string (header)	Access Token For Orion
file * required file (formData)	

Responses Response content type application/json

Code	Description
200	Return array of object with summary of update operations
	<p>Example Value Model</p> <p>application/json</p> <pre>{ "status": [{ "type": "Entity type", "description": { "id": "Entity id" }, "actions": [{ "error": "Error if there was one", "status": "Status of operation", "type": "Type of operation CREATE" }] }] }</pre>
400	The incoming request is invalid in this context. U must select some file
401	The request has not been applied because it lacks valid authentication credentials for the target resource.
415	Request content type is not supported. Please select .csv file
503	There are no server resources to fulfill the client request.

Figure 40 - POST /entities

GET /entities/{entityID}

Get list of entities specifying entityID, Service and ServicePath (see Figure 41).

GET /entities/{entityId} Entity by ID

Retrieves Entity by specifying EntityId, Service and ServicePath

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
entityId * required string (path)	ID of entity to return
Fiware-Service * required string (header)	Service of entities
Fiware-ServicePath * required string (header)	Service Path of entities
X-Auth-Token * required string (header)	Access Token For Orion

Responses Response content type: application/json

Code	Description
200	Single object representing requested entity
401	The request has not been applied because it lacks valid authentication credentials for the target resource.
404	The resource (entity, subscription, etc.) referred in the request has not been found.
503	There are no server resources to fulfill the client request.

```

Example Value | Model
[
  {
    "id": "string",
    "type": "string",
    "name": "string",
    "description": "string",
    "width": 0,
    "height": 0,
    "depth": 0,
    "weight": 0,
    "cargoVolume": 0,
    "maximumLoad": 0,
    "recommendedLoad": 0,
    "category": [
      "string"
    ],
    "insertHolesNumber": 0,
    "insertHolesWidth": 0,
    "loadType": "string",
    "madeOf": "string",
    "madeOfCode": "string",
    "brandName": "string",
    "modelName": "string",
    "manufacturerName": "string",
    "colors": [
      "string"
    ]
  }
]
    
```

Figure 41 - GET/entities/{entityID}

GET /entities/type/{typeID}

Get list of entities specifying typeID, Service and ServicePath (see Figure 42).

GET /entities/type/{typeId} List of Entities by type

Retrieves a list of Entities by specifying EntityType, Service and ServicePath

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
typeid * required string (path)	ID of entity to return
Fiware-Service * required string (header)	Service of entities
Fiware-ServicePath * required string (header)	Service Path of entities
X-Auth-Token * required string (header)	Access Token For Orion

Responses Response content type: application/json

Code	Description
200	<p>Single object representing requested entity</p> <p>Example Value Model</p> <pre>[{ "id": "string", "type": "string", "name": "string", "description": "string", "width": 0, "height": 0, "depth": 0, "weight": 0, "cargoVolume": 0, "maximumLoad": 0, "recommendedLoad": 0, "category": ["string"], "insertHolesNumber": 0, "insertHolesWidth": 0, "loadType": "string", "madeOf": "string", "madeOfCode": "string", "brandName": "string", "modelName": "string", "manufacturerName": "string", "colors": ["string"] }]</pre>
401	The request has not been applied because it lacks valid authentication credentials for the target resource.
404	The resource (entity, subscription, etc.) referred in the request has not been found.
503	There are no server resources to fulfill the client request.

Figure 42 - GET /entities/type/{typeId}

GET /entities/update

Update entities from user supplied file (csv and json) (see Figure 43).

POST /entities/update Update entities from user file

Update entities from user supplied file (csv, json, text)

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
Fiware-Service * required string (header)	Service of entities
Fiware-ServicePath * required string (header)	Service Path of entities
X-Auth-Token * required string (header)	Access Token For Orion
file * required file (formData)	

Responses Response content type: application/json

Code	Description
200	Return array of object with summary of update operations
	<p>Example Value Model</p> <p>application/json</p> <pre>{ "status": [{ "type": "Entity type", "description": { "id": "Entity id" }, "actions": [{ "error": "Error if there was one", "status": "Status of operation", "type": "Type of operation UPDATE" }] }] }</pre>
400	The incoming request is invalid in this context. U must select some file
401	Unauthorized
415	Request content type is not supported. Please select .csv file
503	There are no server resources to fulfill the client request.

Figure 43 - POST /entities/update

GET /rules

Show all rules available in the NGSICConnectorAPI defined in the Data Model. (see Figure 44).

GET /rules List of all available rules

Show all rules available in api defined by model

Parameters Try it out

No parameters

Responses Response content type: application/json

Code	Description
200	Return array of available rules

Example Value | Model

application/json

```
[
  "DepositPoint",
  "DepositPointType",
  "DepositPointIsle",
  "SortingType",
  "Transaction",
  "Vehicle",
  "VehicleType",
  "Waste",
  "WasteCategory"
]
```

Figure 44 - GET /rules

GET /rules/{ruleID}

Get single rule (see Figure 45).

GET /rules{ruleId} Return single rule

Return single rule

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
ruleId * required string (path)	ID of entity to return

Responses Response content type: application/json

Code	Description
200	Return object containing single rule
404	Rule not found

Example Value | Model

application/json

```
{
  "Example": {
    "id": "Mandatory:Text, Unique identifier. Example waste:6",
    "family": "Mandatory:Text, Fixed to Resource",
    "type": "Mandatory:Text, Resource type. In this case fixed to Waste",
    "name": "Mandatory:Text, Waste Name. Example Green glass bottle",
    "description": "Optional:Text, Waste description. Example Bottle made of green glass",
    "refcategory": "Mandatory:Text, Reference to category entity this belongs. Example [wastecategory:9]",
    "definitionSource": "Optional:Text, Where this characterization comes from",
    "wasteCode": "Optional:Text, LER waste code",
    "Forbidden characters": "< > ; ( )"
  }
}
```

Figure 45 - GET /rules/{ruleID}

Annex D – Cygnus Name Mappings

Table 64 presents the list of rules defined in the “*name_mappings*” configuration file of Cygnus.

```
{
  "serviceMappings": [
    {
      "originalService": "waste4think",
      "servicePathMappings": [
        {
          "originalServicePath": "/deusto/w4t/cascais/real",
          "entityMappings": [
            {
              "originalEntityId": ".*",
              "originalEntityType": "DepositPointType",
              "newEntityId": "",
              "newEntityType": "depositpointtype",
              "attributeMappings": []
            },
            {
              "originalEntityId": ".*",
              "originalEntityType": "SortingType",
              "newEntityId": "",
              "newEntityType": "sortingtype",
              "attributeMappings": []
            },
            {
              "originalEntityId": ".*",
              "originalEntityType": "DepositPointIsle",
              "newEntityId": "",
              "newEntityType": "depositpointisle",
              "attributeMappings": []
            },
            {
              "originalEntityId": ".*",
```

```

        "originalEntityType": "DepositPoint",
        "newEntityId": "",
        "newEntityType": "depositpoint",
        "attributeMappings": []
    },
]
},
{
    "originalServicePath": "/deusto/w4t/seveso/real",
    "entityMappings": [
        {
            "originalEntityId": ".*",
            "originalEntityType": "SortingType",
            "newEntityId": "",
            "newEntityType": "sortingtype",
            "attributeMappings": []
        },
        {
            "originalEntityId": ".*",
            "originalEntityType": "VehicleType",
            "newEntityId": "",
            "newEntityType": "vehicletype",
            "attributeMappings": []
        },
        {
            "originalEntityId": ".*",
            "originalEntityType": "Vehicle",
            "newEntityId": "",
            "newEntityType": "vehicle",
            "attributeMappings": []
        },
        {
            "originalEntityId": ".*",
            "originalEntityType": "DepositPoint",
            "newEntityId": "",

```

```

        "newEntityType": "depositpoint",
        "attributeMappings": []
      },
    {
      "originalEntityId": ".*",
      "originalEntityType": "DepositPointType",
      "newEntityId": "",
      "newEntityType": "depositpointtype",
      "attributeMappings": []
    }
  ]
},
{
  "originalServicePath": "/deusto/w4t/zamudio/real",
  "entityMappings": [
    {
      "originalEntityId": ".*",
      "originalEntityType": "SortingType",
      "newEntityId": "",
      "newEntityType": "sortingtype",
      "attributeMappings": []
    },
    {
      "originalEntityId": ".*",
      "originalEntityType": "VehicleType",
      "newEntityId": "",
      "newEntityType": "vehicletype",
      "attributeMappings": []
    },
    {
      "originalEntityId": ".*",
      "originalEntityType": "Vehicle",
      "newEntityId": "",
      "newEntityType": "vehicle",
      "attributeMappings": []
    }
  ]
}

```

```
    },  
    {  
      "originalEntityId": ".*",  
      "originalEntityType": "DepositPoint",  
      "newEntityId": "",  
      "newEntityType": "depositpoint",  
      "attributeMappings": []  
    },  
    {  
      "originalEntityId": ".*",  
      "originalEntityType": "DepositPointType",  
      "newEntityId": "",  
      "newEntityType": "depositpointtype",  
      "attributeMappings": []  
    }  
  ]  
}  
]  
}
```

Table 64 - W4T Cygnus Name Mappings file

Comments from External Reviewers

External Reviewer #1

18/10/2018

Issue	Score		Comments
	Yes	No	
Is the format of the document correct?	X	4	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X	4	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X	4	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X	4	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X	3	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X	3	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X	4	
Are the indexes correct?	X	4	
Is the written English correct?	X	4	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X	4	
Glossary present in the document?	X	4	

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Comments from External Reviewers

External Reviewer #2

19/10/2018

Issue	Score		Comments
	Yes	No	
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5
Are the indexes correct?	X		5
Is the written English correct?	X		4 Minor corrections
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5
Glossary present in the document?	X		5

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Comments from External Reviewers

External Reviewer #3

24-10-2018

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x		5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x		4	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x		4	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	x		5	
Are the indexes correct?	x		5	
Is the written English correct?	x		5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	x		5	
Glossary present in the document?	x		5	

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